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Research on breast cancer induced chronic conditions
supported by causal analysis of multi-source data

D1.3 – Legal, ethical and operational framework

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

AI	artificial intelligence
AI Act	Artificial Intelligence Act
API	application programming interface
BCP	Breast Cancer Patients
cApp	companion application
CCC	complex chronic conditions
CISP	Cloud Infrastructure Service Provider
CRF	case report format
DGA	Data Governance Act
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EHR	electronic health records
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPU	graphics processing unit
MDR	Medical Devices Regulation
pApp	patient application
PBCB	Prospective Breast Cancer Biobank
RCT	randomized clinical trials
RWD	Real World Data
SQRBC	Swedish Quality Registry for Breast Cancer
UI	user interface

Disclaimer

"The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable are written by the consortium partners under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme "Research on BrEast Cancer induced chronic conditions supported by Causal Analysis of multi-source data" aka REBECCA (under the grant agreement no 965231) and do not necessarily reflect the views expressed by the European Commission.

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Executive Summary

Using real-world data in clinical research aiming to improve the quality of life and clinical management of cancer patients introduces several legal, ethical and operational challenges that need to be addressed.

The aim of this deliverable D1.3 (“Legal, ethical and operational framework” report) is to provide an overview of the European and national frameworks for handling legal and ethical issues in Horizon 2020 research and innovation projects, and in REBECCA in particular. It describes the legal and ethical restraints as well as operational and patient requirements, that should be addressed by the partners when designing REBECCA, so as to ensure the project’s compliance with the applicable laws and regulations. It sequentially discusses the relevant EU laws (such as the General Data Protection Regulation, the ePrivacy directive, the Medical Devices Regulation, the NIS directive or the latest EC’s initiatives under the European data strategy) and their impact on REBECCA. In particular, this report points out the major challenges arising under the said legislation in the context of REBECCA and how the partners should handle those. It will then move to analyse the ethical standards applicable in research, so as to enable partners to implement appropriate measures in order to avoid ethical concerns while implementing REBECCA. Lastly, the report will focus on the operational restrictions (identified by the technical partners) and patient requirements (identified by the clinical partners and the patients themselves) and how these are going to be addressed by the REBECCA partners when designing REBECCA system.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This deliverable contains critical information regarding the legal, ethical and operational restrictions and requirements of the REBECCA action. More specifically, according to the Description of Task 1.3. this deliverable's aim is to identify and document:

- legal restrictions that apply regarding the use of different types of data for the purposes of the clinical research in REBECCA, including data ownership and controllership responsibilities, and data protection and privacy rules and obligations, especially GDPR compliance;
- the ethical considerations that need to be taken into account when designing and implementing the clinical studies, including the applications for ethical approvals and the appropriate involvement of research participants/patients in the clinical study based on non-discriminatory selection criteria, obtaining informed consent and respect for human rights and dignity;
- operational or patient restrictions and requirements, based on patient needs and the patient management processes that take place in the participating clinics.

1.2 Methodology

Methodologically, this will be done by analysing REBECCA from a legal, ethical, and operational perspective and drawing requirements pertaining to these, and arising under the applicable laws, regulations, policies and guidance documents. This deliverable should not be seen as a fully mature and exhaustive document, but rather as a first overview of essential challenges, requirements and compliance strategies that will be continued throughout the project, based on additional input from REBECCA partners and the further identification of relevant factors and regulatory processes at the EU and national level.

1.3 Structure

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 briefly discusses the essence of REBECCA project;
- Section 3 begins with the legal analysis of the REBECCA action with special emphasis on privacy and data protection compliance, Medical Devices Regulation as applied to the project, as well as the cybersecurity related

obligations of health care providers/operators of essential services; it also touches upon the IP rights to background and results of the REBECCA project as well as briefly discusses the latest EC's initiative – the European Data Act, which could possibly apply to the data generated by REBECCA;

- Section 4 discusses issues related to ethics in research in general and in HORIZON 2020 projects such as REBECCA - in particular;
- Section 5 elaborates on the operational and patient raised restrictions and requirements, to be taken into account when designing the REBECCA system;
- Section 6 concludes this deliverable.

1.4 Targeted Audience

The intended audience for this deliverable is preliminarily the REBECCA consortium partners, as the work contained in this document will support the implementation of the REBECCA action. However, the research work regarding the European Union (EU) regulatory frameworks on privacy and protection of personal data as well as the national legal and ethical frameworks in the REBECCA clinical studies countries (i.e. Sweden, Norway, Spain) might be of interest to a wider audience (e.g. policy makers, researchers, general public).

1.5 Interactions

The scope of this Deliverable 1.3. overlaps to a certain extent with the following deliverables under REBECCA:

- D1.1 - User requirements and use-cases (as far as the "Operational and patient restrictions and requirements" are concerned)
- D1.2 - REBECCA co-creation methodology and plan (as far as the "Operational and patient restrictions and requirements" are concerned)
- D2.1 - Initial System Specifications. (as far as "Web based user profiling" and REBECCA system's security requirements are concerned)
- D10.3 - POPD - Requirement No. 4. (as far as web based user profiling, pseudonymisation techniques and security measures used within REBECCA, or the necessity to conduct a DPIA are concerned).

Where relevant and in order to avoid duplication, this deliverable will refer to these other REBECCA deliverables.

2 About REBECCA

REBECCA Project (REsearch on BrEast Cancer induced chronic conditions supported by Causal Analysis of multi-source data/REBECCA) is an EU-funded project that taps into the potential of Real-World Data (RWD) for supporting clinical research on Complex Chronic Conditions (CCC) as a complement to Randomized Controlled Trials (RCT). REBECCA moves beyond the analysis of Electronic Health Records (EHR), by combining it with detailed monitoring data from multiple wearables, online behaviour and registry data to monitor patients' functional, emotional and Quality of Life trajectories, with high temporal granularity. By combining retrospective registry and episodic medical data with continuous monitoring streams, REBECCA will obtain deeper insights for enhancing clinical outcomes on chronic complex conditions in the domain of breast cancer post-treatment management.

REBECCA also proposes explainable causal modelling combined with deep learning to account for observed and latent confounders in RWD analysis. The project will focus on the complex array of chronic comorbidities developed during breast cancer recovery, in particular studying the impact of primary and adjuvant cancer treatment on patients' quality of life and assessing the value of detailed patient monitoring as a means for improved patient care, and will also demonstrate the extensibility of REBECCA to other forms of cancer (such as prostate cancer).

The data used in REBECCA will be deployed within 7 clinical studies in 3 countries (Sweden, Norway and Spain), with over 650 individuals being involved, and will produce new knowledge on clinical management of cancer patients that will shape future guidelines and practices for post-cancer treatments:

- 3 observational studies for comorbidities associated with cancer (Sweden, Norway, Spain)¹
- 3 interventional studies to examine improvement in quality of life of patients using REBECCA as compared to standard treatment (Sweden, Norway, Spain)
- 1 feasibility study for prostate cancer patients in Norway.

Best practices resulting from the REBECCA studies will be then disseminated to researchers, public health and regulatory bodies throughout Europe to facilitate wider adoption of RWD in clinical research.

¹ Breast cancer treatment-induced peripheral neuropathy (Sweden); Breast cancer-related fatigue (Norway); Adjuvant treatment-induced osteopenia/osteoporosis (Spain);

In addition, the REBECCA platform, capable of detailed monitoring and privacy-preserving federated cross-country data analysis, will provide an infrastructure for continued progress on use of RWD beyond the end of the project.

Through these activities, REBECCA aims at the mass adoption of RWD for understanding chronic complex conditions and ultimately at establishing RWD as a valuable clinical research and patient management tool.

As such REBECCA raises a number of ethical issues and privacy concerns which are addressed in detail throughout this deliverable.

3 Legal framework

3.1 Data protection

3.1.1 Data collected by REBECCA

REBECCA project will collect multi-source real world data:

- Data from electronic health records collected at the clinics (i.e. blood examinations, standardized questionnaires at the clinical sites)
- Data from patients' wearables (i.e. physical activity, sleep, heart rate, stress, meals detected, stress factors)
- Data from patient and companion mobile apps (self-reported data such as annotated photos of the patient meals, surroundings, stressing factors such as e.g. traffic, ad hoc questionnaires and continuous, objective and unobtrusive monitoring of location);
- Data from web browser plugin (which allows to track the patient's emotional/well-being status through the monitoring of the patient's online activity)

Additionally, REBECCA will also take advantage of publicly available information and datasets such as:

- Data on local environment of the patient (i.e. data from open and public data sources e.g. maps, satellites, statistical authorities, in order to quantify the life-space of the patient, i.e. where the patient spends most of her/his time during the day, does he/she go to parks, gyms, restaurants, recreational facilities).

All of the above data will be acquired and processed by the REBECCA 360° monitoring platform, supporting interfaces for the diverse set of REBECCA sources and a set of transformation (ETL) operations, mapping data into a common representation format. Signal processing, machine learning and natural language data processing will allow REBECCA to analyse and make sense of over 200 variables, including clinical, behavioural, emotional and living environment indicators.

3.1.2 Actors and responsibilities

The below tables list the key partners to the REBECCA consortium and describe their respective responsibilities², in particular in the context of data sharing and data use:

² As set out in the Grant Agreement no 965231 – REBECCA – H2020-SC1-BHC-2018-2020/H2020-SC1-2020-Single-Stage-RTD

Table 1 – Clinical partners

<i>Clinical Partner/Data provider</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>Major role in the project</i>
KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET (KI)	Sweden	Involvement in the conceptual description of the system and in the behavioural monitoring (emotional and functional life capacities) analysis and modelling of the patient lives. Coordinator for need finding and the ethical monitoring of the project. KI will coordinate the two studies in Stockholm and the acquisition of retrospective data from the Swedish Quality Registry for Breast Cancer (SQRBC) and other Swedish national registries.
Helse Stavanger HF (SUH)	Norway	Major clinical partner in REBECCA, SUH provides input for the creation of the causal models and effort for the use of Norwegian retrospective data repositories, specifically the Prospective Breast Cancer Biobank (PBCB) SUH will be responsible for the performance of the

		Norwegian branch of the clinical studies, and the additional Prostate Cancer feasibility trial for evaluating the extensibility of the REBECCA use in male patients and other cancers.
Fundación para la Investigación del Hospital Clínico de la Comunidad Valenciana (INCLIVA)	Spain	Third major clinical partner in REBECCA. INCLIVA will perform the two Spanish trials and will lead the efforts for the realization of the intervention studies for improved patient outcomes through RWD use. INCLIVA participates in the system design and integration, by offering the clinical perspective to the process; it contributes to the creation of the causal inference models and the analysis of local, hospital-based retrospective data.
Bröstcancerföreningen Amazona I Stockholms län (Amazona)	Sweden	Amazona provides patient input through their own members and coordinates the efforts for continuous feedback and co-creation (this includes organization of the co-creation workshops and focus groups, the dissemination

		<p>of online surveys). AMAZONA will have a major dissemination role in the project, as the natural carriers of the REBECCA message towards the wider patient population, supporting the stakeholder engagement of the project within that framework.</p>
<p>Region Stockholm (RSTO)</p>	<p>Sweden</p>	<p>RSTO has a distinct clinical role, providing information about the needs of the system and the framework of its functionality, while participating in the continuous co-creation process. RSTO also has a significant contribution for the extraction of Swedish registry datasets. Significant effort will be dedicated in the clinical data collection during the Chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy (CIPN) study and RSTO will also handle the patient recruitment in the intervention study in Stockholm.</p>

Table 2 – Technical partners

<i>Technical partner</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>Major role in the project</i>
ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO OF THESSALONIKIS (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki) (AUTH)	Greece	A major role in the project both as project coordinator and core technical partner. AUTH is in charge of the technical, financial and administrative management. It leads in the process of translating user needs and scenarios into functional requirements, non-functional requirements and use-cases of the REBECCA system. AUTH develops the patient and companion applications , leads the development of the behaviour, clinical and environment indicator extraction technologies of REBECCA and the associated cloud modules of the REBECCA platform.
Ethniko Kentro Erevnas kai Technologikis Anaptyxis – Center for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH)	Greece	CERTH leads the development of algorithms and tools for detailed and continuous monitoring of cancer patients (the REBECCA 360° platform); especially it is responsible for the extraction of social media and web indicators of the emotional state and

		<p>quality of life of patients. It will also lead the development of the REBECCA edge monitoring components. CERTH will also take part in the development of the REBECCA data analysis components. Finally, CERTH will also contribute to system design, technical integration and testing and dissemination and exploitation.</p>
<p>CHAROKOPEIO PANEPISTIMIO - Harokopio University of Athens (HUA)</p>	Greece	<p>HUA leads the work in developing the methodology for causal modelling of RWD, including methodologies for causal inference and prediction. HUA develops explainable causal models for breast cancer-related chronic conditions and will use them to perform an analysis of retrospective biobank and registry data. It will lead the cross-country analysis of prospective data from Sweden, Norway and Spain, using both aggregated data sharing and federated learning technologies.</p>
<p>NETCOMPANY INTRASOFT SA (INTRA)</p>	Luxembourg	<p>INTRA leads the REBECCA platform architecture and</p>

		<p>design specification, following a security and privacy-by-design approach, as well as continuous integration and testing activities to release the operational versions of the integrated platform to support the relevant clinical studies during piloting. INTRA will lead the development of the clinicians/researchers dashboard, as well as innovation management activities and will contribute to user requirements analysis, dissemination and exploitation tasks, as well as technically support the execution of the envisioned clinical studies.</p>
<p>EIGHT BELLS LTD(8BELLS)</p>	<p>Cyprus</p>	<p>The 8BELLS team leads the task of building interfaces for data acquisition from the multiple REBECCA data sources and mapping them into a common data representation format. 8BELLS will also lead the cost-benefit analysis of REBECCA which will provide concise evidence on the financial benefits of adoption of REBECCA</p>

		<p>and RWD for clinical research, as well as for patient monitoring and management. It will participate in the project's horizontal activities, including dissemination and exploitation of the project's progress and results.</p>
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In order to achieve the goals of the REBECCA Action, some of the consortium members (i.e. the Data Providers), will collect, use and share with other consortium members (i.e. Technical Partners) certain personal data (including but not limited to personal data related to health) of the research participants.

3.1.3 Concept of a controller, joint controller and processor

The concepts of controller, joint controller and processor play a crucial role in the application of data protection laws, since they determine who shall be responsible for compliance with different data protection rules, and how data subjects can exercise their rights in practice.

Controller/joint controller

Under the GDPR a controller means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data³. Where two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of processing, they shall be the so-called "joint controllers". As such they are obliged by the GDPR to determine – in a transparent manner - their respective responsibilities for compliance with the obligations under the GDPR, in particular as regards the exercising of the rights of the data subjects and their respective duties to provide the information referred to in Articles 13 and 14, by means of an arrangement between them unless, and in so far as, the respective responsibilities of the controllers are determined by Union or Member State law to which the controllers are subject.

In the context of REBECCA virtually all of the consortium members (excluding Timelex and EHMA) process personal data of the REBECCA research participants in one way or

³ Article 4(7) of the GDPR

the other. More importantly, all consortium members jointly determine the means and purposes of such processing, that is why and how the data is processed. As a result they meet the definition of “joint controllers” under Article 26 of the GDP and as such should conclude a proper agreement, that will duly set forth and organize their respective rights and obligation with respect to the data collected, exchanged and generated within the REBECCA project.

As required under the GDPR, the essential elements of such an agreement should be made available to the data subjects. In the context of REBECCA, the essence of the joint controllership agreement should be made available to the research participants (as well as their companions, where applicable), for example through the consent form.

Processor

Next to the concept of controller, the GDPR introduces the concept of a processor, i.e. a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller.

According to the European Data Protection Board’s (EDPB) “Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR”⁴ there are two basic conditions for qualifying as processor: that it is a separate entity in relation to the controller and that it processes personal data on the controller’s behalf. The processor must not process the data otherwise than according to the controller’s instructions. A processor will be infringing the GDPR if it goes beyond the controller’s instructions and starts to determine its own purposes and means of the processing (in which case it will be considered a controller in respect of that processing and may be subject to sanctions for going beyond the controller’s instructions).

When entrusting processing to processors, a controller must use only processors providing sufficient guarantees to implement appropriate technical and organizational measures so that the processing will meet the requirements of the GDPR and ensure the protection of the rights of the data subject. Moreover, the processing shall be governed by an agreement, which will set forth the subject matter and duration of the processing, the nature and purpose of processing, the type of personal data and categories of data subjects as well as the obligations and rights of the controller. In particular a data processing agreement shall stipulate that the processor:

- processes data only on documented instructions from the controller;
- ensures that persons authorised to process data have committed themselves to confidentiality;

4

https://edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2021-07/edpb_guidelines_202007_controllerprocessor_final_en.pdf

- implements appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk;
- respects the conditions for engaging another processor;
- assists the controller in the fulfilment of the controller's obligations;
- deletes or returns all personal data to the controller at the end of the provision of services relating to processing and deletes existing copies;
- makes available to the controller all information necessary to demonstrate compliance with the obligations under the GDPR and contribute to audits and inspections conducted by the controller or its auditors.

In the context of REBECCA, if at any point the joint controllers (jointly) or any of them separately engages any third party (-ies) (subcontractors) to process personal data on their behalf, those third parties will very likely meet the definition of a "processor" within the meaning of the GDPR. As a result, a data processing agreement will have to be concluded between the joint controller (-s) and the given subcontractor. This will be the case in particular with to the dedicated private cloud platform, that the REBECCA partners plan to maintain and which will be hosted on virtual machines as compute nodes on IaaS provider (i.e. Hetzner). As a general rule, cloud infrastructure service providers (CISPs) are processors within the meaning of the GDPR.

CISPs provide self-service, on-demand cloud infrastructure. It is the customer who chooses if and how to use this infrastructure, including whether any personal data is uploaded to the cloud infrastructure service, and if so, how that personal data is "processed". CISPs have no control over what content the customer chooses to upload to the service (including whether or not it includes personal data). CISPs have no role in the decision- making as to whether or not the customer uses the cloud infrastructure service for processing personal data and for what purpose. Accordingly, CISPs are not able to ascertain whether there may be a lawful basis for the processing. As such, their responsibility is to (a) comply with the customer's instructions as provided for in the service contract and (b) provide information about the service.⁵

Since it will be the REBECCA consortium that chooses to store or otherwise process personal data using a CISP's services, and determines the purposes and means of such

⁵ Data protection Code of conduct for cloud infrastructure service providers dated 9 February 2021 available at https://www.codeofconduct.cloud/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/2021_CISPE_Cloud_IaaS_Data_Protection_Code_of_Conduct_-_GDPR_Compliance_EN_clean.pdf#:~:text=IaaS%20providers%20are%20referred%20in%20this%20Code,personal%20data%20that%20the%20customer%20wishes%20to%20perform.

processing, the CISP (i.e. Hetzner) will be the REBECCA consortium's processor and the REBECCA partners will be the data controllers (joint controllers).

This will require the conclusion of a data processing agreement with the CISP (i.e. Hetzner) as required under Article 28 of the GDPR, which will define the features of the service and how it is delivered and the respective rights and obligations of the CISP as regards the processing of the personal data to be stored within the REBECCA (or the inclusion of relevant provisions in the underlying service agreement).

3.1.4 Identification of data flows within REBECCA

The REBECCA project aims to develop a digital cloud platform (REBECCA 360° tool) for breast cancer patients, that will be able to monitor their everyday physical and emotional state.

Raw data for continuous monitoring of the patient quality of life will be collected from various sources such as wearable devices, mobile applications⁶, web browser plugin. Data from the patients' electronic health records (medical history and/or biological sample data) will be extracted to be combined with the above data. REBECCA will also use open and public data sources (such as maps, satellites, statistical authorities) to quantify the life-space of the patient (e.g. whether the patient uses sports/recreational facilities, whether she goes to restaurants, cafes or whether she mostly stays home).

The collection of datasets will be stored in REBECCA cloud⁷ databases and will be available for analysis that will provide results about the patient's lifestyle, behaviour, medical history, and possible identifications of changes in functional and emotional status. This in turn would allow the medical experts/patient's doctor to modify treatment/follow-up/provide support/counselling.

The evaluation of analysed data and the overall patients' status will be available through a web user interface that will form the clinical dashboard, available to the clinicians and medical experts at the clinical sites in Norway, Sweden and Spain.

REBECCA will handle patient data at different aggregation layers including: (i) data handled only at the edge device, (ii) detailed behavioural indicators, registry data and clinical data, which will be stored securely in local data storage facilities (clinical sites/RedCap servers), and (iii) pseudonymized patient indicators which, under specific

⁶ Both patient and companion apps

⁷ A dedicated private cloud platform maintained by the consortium members will be hosted on virtual machines as compute nodes on IaaS provider (i.e. Hetzner) with data centers located within the EU (i.e. Germany).

conditions can be shared across countries (e.g. with technical partners) for research purposes (e.g. training algorithms, causal model analysis).

The data ingested in the REBECCA platform will be pseudonymized: a unique ID will be assigned to the patient, with the key allowing to re-identify the patient being held outside the REBECCA system (i.e. at the clinical site/by the patient's doctor). Yet, the REBECCA 360° platform will have no communication with any systems that may already exist in the clinical partners' sites (clinics). Clinical data will be inserted into REBECCA using data entry forms or using files (e.g., database exports, CSV files).

The below figure explains the data flows within REBECCA.

Figure 1 Data flows within REBECCA

Deliverable D2.1 “Initial System Specifications” present in further detail the REBECCA system components, data types that are stored or generated within each one of those components, as well as the respective data flows in between them.

3.1.5 Key principles of data protection

Article 5 of the GDPR sets out seven key principles which lie at the heart of the general data protection regime and which must be always respected by data controllers. These are as follows:

- Principle of **lawfulness, fairness and transparency** towards the data subject

What it means under the GDPR: The data subject must be informed of the existence of the processing operation and its purposes; this encompasses the right to be provided information on the identity of the controller and the purposes of the processing, as well as of the data subjects right to obtain information as to which personal data of his/her are being processed. Where the personal data are collected from the data subject, the data subject should also be informed whether he or she is obliged to provide the personal data and of the consequences, where he or she does not provide such data. This principle requires also that any information and communication relating to the processing of the data subject's personal data be easily accessible and understandable, and that clear and plain language be used. In cases where this is applicable - the data subject should also be informed of the existence of profiling and the consequences thereof.

What it means under the REBECCA: In the contexts of REBECCA, the transparency principle translates into the patients` right to be adequately informed of the processing of their data. As a result, data controllers must inform the patient of the data processing via a proper information notice, in advance of the commencement of any processing operations. Contents of such information notice are described in detail in section - "Information notice" below.

- Principle of purpose limitation

What it means under the GDPR: Data must be collected for a specified, explicit and legitimate purpose and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with this original purpose. Processing of personal data for purposes other than those for which they were initially collected should be allowed only where the processing is compatible with that initial purpose, in which case, no separate legal basis is required.

In cases where the REBECCA partners would want to process the personal data of the research participants for purposes other than those of the REBECCA

project, they would have to ascertain whether this new purpose of further processing is compatible with the purpose for which the personal data are initially collected (taking into account any link between this original initial purpose and the purpose of the intended further processing; the context in which the personal data have been collected, including in particular the reasonable expectations of research participants, as to their further use; the nature of the personal data; the consequences of the intended further processing for research participants; and the existence of appropriate safeguards in both the original and intended further processing operations. Where the data subject has given consent to process his/her personal data, the controller should be allowed to further process such personal data irrespective of the compatibility of the purposes.

What it means under REBECCA: In the context of REBECCA this means that the consortium members cannot use the research participants' data for any other purposes than those conveyed to the research participants at the time of inclusion/collection of their data, unless the basis for processing of such data is consent and the research participants have been properly informed of such further processing.

- Principle of data minimization/proportionality

What it means under the GDPR: Personal data should be processed only if the purpose of the processing could not reasonably be fulfilled by other means. Moreover, the data processed should be adequate, relevant and limited to what is absolutely necessary for the purposes for which they are processed.

What it means under REBECCA: In the context of REBECCA, partners should assess whether all of the data that they plan to collect and process within the REBECCA are indeed necessary to achieve/fulfil their intended purposes (such as for example the improvement of the patients' quality of life or research purposes). Special concern should be given to the anticipated processing of patient location type data that the REBECCA 360° platform is going to ingest to quantify the patient's life-space and whether the processing of this data is necessary to achieve the intended purpose of REBECCA. For more details on the use of location data please see section "Use of location data by REBECCA" below.

- Principle of **accuracy**

What it means under the GDPR: Data should be accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date.

What it means under the REBECCA: Personal data of the research participants should be accurate at all times and kept up-to-date. Any data that is no longer accurate (considering the purpose for which it was collected and processed) should be either rectified or deleted from the REBECCA system.

- Principle of storage limitation

What it means under the GDPR: This requires ensuring that the period for which the personal data are stored is limited to a strict minimum and that the data is kept for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which it were processed. In order to ensure that the personal data are not kept longer than necessary, time limits should be established by the controller for erasure or for a periodic review. GDPR allows for the processing of personal data beyond the set retention periods in certain explicitly stated situations, one of them being the processing of data solely for scientific research purposes (in accordance with Article 89(1) of the GDPR).

What it means under the REBECCA: In the context of REBECCA partners should ensure that the data retention periods are not excessive and that the data is not processed indefinitely. Specifically, they should ensure that upon the completion of the REBECCA project, the data of the research participants is deleted or irreversibly anonymized. Processing data beyond the lifespan of the REBECCA project can be possible only for scientific research purposes and subject to appropriate technical and organizational measures being implemented to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the research participants.

- Principle of security and confidentiality

What it means under the GDPR: Personal data should be processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security and confidentiality of the personal data, including for preventing unauthorised access to or use of personal data and the equipment used for the processing.

What it means under REBECCA: In the context of REBECCA partners will have to implement appropriate technical and organizational measures that will ensure a level of security appropriate to the risks. In order to maintain security and to prevent processing that would be in violation of the GDPR, the REBECCA partners should evaluate the risks inherent in the processing and implement measures to mitigate those, such as encryption or pseudonymisation. Those measures should ensure an appropriate level of security, including confidentiality, taking into account the state of the art and the costs of implementation in relation to the risks and the nature of the personal data to be protected. In assessing data security risk, REBECCA partners should consider the following risks: accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed within REBECCA system, which may in particular lead to physical, material or non-material damage.

- Principle of accountability

What it means under the GDPR: Controllers must always observe the above principles but also be ready to demonstrate this compliance vis-à-vis the authorities.

What it means under REBECCA: In the context of REBECCA, in order to meet the requirement of accountability, the joint controllers should put in place appropriate technical and organizational measures. These include in particular:

- adopting and implementing appropriate protection policies;
- taking a data protection by design and default approach;
- putting written contracts in place with third parties (vendors) who process personal data on behalf of the data controllers;
- maintaining documentation of processing activities (such as records of data processing operations);

- implementing appropriate security measures (e.g. encryption, pseudonymisation);
- recording and, where necessary, reporting personal data breaches;
- carrying out data protection impact assessments for uses of personal data that are likely to result in high risk to individuals' interests;
- appointing a DPO.

3.1.6 Legal basis for data processing

Consent

In accordance with one of the key tenets of the GDPR - any data processing must be lawful ("principle of lawfulness"). As stated in Article 6 of the GDPR, processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of legal basis, enumerated in the GDPR, applies. These include in particular the data subject consent, the necessity of the processing for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, if not overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subjects.

In the context of REBECCA, it is the data subject's consent that constitutes the legal basis legitimizing the processing of the personal data of the REBECCA research participants.

As defined under the GDPR, consent means: "any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her".

To be considered a valid legal basis for processing, consent under Article 6 of the GDPR must meet all of the above requirements, that is it must be:

- Free

This is the first and the foremost element to guarantee the control of data subject over their personal data, and means that the data subject should not feel pressured, compelled or in any way coerced to agree to the processing of

his/her personal data⁸. It should be made clear to the data subjects that no adverse consequences will be triggered if they refuse to consent to data processing.

In the context of REBECCA, this means that it must be made abundantly clear to the research participant that their habitual health care regimen will not be negatively impacted by their refusal to participate in the REBECCA study.

- Specific

This means that the data subject has the possibility to consent to each purpose of processing separately; each specific, explicit and legitimate purpose of the intended processing activity must be clearly conveyed to the data subject (an opt-in option must be provided to the data subject with respect to each one of the purposes). The controller must provide data subjects with specific information as to each one of those purposes, so as sensitize them to each of their choices and the impact thereof.

In the context of REBECCA, the consent form must clearly indicate the specific purposes of processing (i.e. include a clear description of the research process understandable to a layperson). And so, the research participants (i.e. BCPs) should be informed (in a comprehensible manner) of the particular purpose for which the particular data will be processed. For example, it should be clarified to them, that their online activity will be monitored for the purpose of assessing their emotional status/well-being or that their location data will be processed to quantify their life-space.

- Informed

⁸Consent will be free when there is no imbalance of power between the controller and the data subject (e.g. patient – doctor, employer – employee), when the consent is not a condition to obtain a service from the controller or access certain functionalities, when the data subject has a clear understanding of all the purposes for which the consent is sought, and the data subject has the possibility to reject or object to some of the purposes. Controller must be able to demonstrate that there will be no negative impact to the data subject if he/she decides not to consent to the processing of personal data (e.g. that the patient's habitual health care regimen will not be negatively impacted by his/her refusal to participate in REBECCA).

An informed consent is linked to the principle of transparency of processing, already discussed above. To understand the processing, the data subject must be informed about its main components. The data subjects must receive at least information concerning the identity of the data controller(s), the purpose(s) of processing, the intended legal basis for processing (e.g. consent), the categories of data processed, the categories of recipient of the data processed, and - where applicable - whether the personal data will be transferred outside of the European Economic Area. This information must be provided in a clear and accessible language, in a manner ensuring that data subject will always have easy access to the above information.

In the context of REBECCA, the research participants should be provided with the above indicated information, at the time of collection of their data (at the latest; preferably at the time of inclusion), in their national language (e.g. Swedish, Norwegian or Spanish). They should also receive their own copy of the information notice (e.g. in paper or electronic form, such as an e-mailed pdf file). The information notice could also be made available on the REBECCA's website/the REBECCA mobile app. Also, should REBECCA process personal data of patients' companions' (e.g. name, surname, e-mail address, contact details, relation to the patient), then the companion should also be provided with the adequate information notice.

- Unambiguous

Consent requires a statement from the data subject or a clear affirmative act; this means that it must always be given through an active motion or an explicit declaration. Consent may be collected either in writing or through a verbal recording. It may also be collected electronically. In any case however, it must be clear to the data subject that they are granting consent to their data processing. In practice, this boils down to data subject signing a consent form. Affirmative action may be taken not only by placing a signature, but also by ticking a box, writing a short statement or another statement or conduct which clearly indicates in this context the data subject's accepts the proposed processing of his or her personal data. Silence, pre-ticked boxes or inactivity should not therefore constitute consent. Controllers must be able to demonstrate that the data subject has granted his/her consent, as part of the accountability obligation. Therefore, the consent process must take into account

the storage of the proof of consent for a specific duration (the retention periods must be included in the information provided to the data subjects).

In the context of REBECCA, research participants should sign the consent form.

- Explicit (in case of special categories of data)

Given the purpose and object of the REBECCA action, the majority of the personal data collected from the research participants will concern their physical health and activity⁹. As such, additional requirements for consent under Article 9 of the GDPR shall apply to the processing of those “special categories data” within REBECCA¹⁰.

As specified in Article 9.1 of the GDPR, special categories of data encompass “personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation”.

Health data self-evidently includes medical records, information about diagnosis or treatment and medical history. But it may also include other information such as whether an individual wears glasses, whether he smokes or drinks, his IQ, any allergies, any support groups he attends, any tax deductions for home alterations and medical product purchase history. The data do not have to be collected on a medical device and do not have to indicate poor health. When conclusions about an individual's health status are drawn as a result of combining non-health data (e.g. lifestyle data) they become health data.¹¹

⁹ Such as step count, heart rate, sleep tracking.

¹⁰ Article 4.15 of the GDPR.

¹¹ A pedometer that measures the number of steps a user takes each day in isolation does not collect health data, but in combination with body mass index and mood data could build up a picture of an individual's health state; see the Article 29 Working Party's answer to the European Commission on the

Due to the particularly sensitive nature, processing of special categories of data is more likely to create risks to the rights and freedoms of the data subjects concerned. As such, it is prohibited as a matter of principle (see Article 9.1 GDPR). However, certain limited exceptions to this outright ban exist under the GDPR, including, in particular, the **explicit consent** of the data subject (Article 9.2 (a) GDPR).

Given that consent is already sought for ethics purposes, and because it is used as a legal basis for the processing of other, non-sensitive categories of personal data, the **explicit consent** (under article 9.2 (a) of the GDPR) appears to be the most appropriate grounds for processing of special categories of data (i.e. health related data) within the REBECCA framework.

According to the EDPB in its Guidelines on Consent¹², the term “explicit” refers to the way consent is expressed by the data subject and means that the data subject must give an express statement of consent. The “explicitness” threshold will usually be reached through a signed written statement of the data subject. However, where necessary, explicit consent may also be obtained with an oral confirmation of consent, that is recorded for evidentiary purposes.

As a consequence, the consent for processing both physical and mental health related data of research participants must not only meet the general criteria for consent (as set forth above), but it must also be conveyed in an explicit manner

Consent for processing vs Informed consent to participate in a research study

Although oftentimes both are collected in one consent form, the consent to the processing of personal data should be clearly distinguished from the consent to the participation in a research study (the latter being a separate ethics related requirement). Therefore, the REBECCA partners should make sure, that both consents are collected from the research participants and bear in mind, that obtaining one does not waive the obligation to collect the other. More on consent in the context of research participation, can be found in Section 3.3.4 “Informed consent”.

3.1.7 Definition and implementation of organizational and technical measures

It is a duty of every controller, to comply with the GDPR, in particular to implement appropriate safeguards for the rights and freedoms of the data subjects, whose data

clarification of the definition of “health data” in relation to lifestyle/wellbeing apps and wearable devices https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/other-document/files/2015/20150205_letter_art29wp_ec_health_data_after_plenary_annex_en.pdf

¹² https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/file1/edpb_guidelines_202005_consent_en.pdf

they process (this duty being mandated also with respect to scientific research projects, such as REBECCA, as provided in Article 89.1 of the GDPR).

Complying with Article 89.1. of the GDPR opens the door to the facilitations provided by the GDPR for scientific research, such as flexibility in the implementation of the principles of purpose limitation or storage limitation.

Pursuant to Article 32 GDPR, it is the responsibility of controllers/joint controllers to implement technical and organizational measures to ensure the level of security appropriate to the risks, including in particular:

- pseudonymisation and encryption of personal data;
- the ability to ensure the ongoing confidentiality, availability and resilience of processing systems and services;
- the ability to restore availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident;
- a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organizational measures for ensuring the security of the processing.

In the context of scientific research¹³, GDPR (in its Article 89.1) emphasizes the importance of, in particular, the following safeguards for the rights and freedoms of the data subject:

- the principle of data minimization, which supposes the minimal collection of data and minimal processing of the data collected (already discussed in Section 3.1.5 above);
- pseudonymisation (pseudonymisation is a reversible, de-identifying procedure, the purpose of which is to ensure that personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information (Article 4.5 GDPR). Through pseudonymisation, a personally identifiable information within a data record are replaced by one or more artificial identifiers/pseudonyms. Any additional information that could be used to re-identify the data subject must be kept separately and be subject to technical and organizational measures, so as to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.)

Bearing in mind the above, the REBECCA partners should strive to implement the above mentioned safeguarding measures.

¹³ EDPB Guidelines 03/2020 on the processing of data concerning health for the purpose of scientific research in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak; https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/guidelines-032020-processing-data-concerning-health-purpose_en

In the context of REBECCA, a detailed description of the security requirements and procedures to be implemented is contained in D2.1 “Initial systems specifications”. In particular, Section 5 of that deliverable elaborates on the Security Requirements, (e.g. log management, system hardening, user authentication, application security) including privacy filters (e.g. data encryption, data pseudonymisation etc.), that will be covered within the REBECCA platform and which are essential for hosting sensitive clinical data on a cloud platform solution.

3.1.8 Information notice

As discussed above, transparency of the processing is one of the fundamental principles of data protection and requires that the data subjects (i.e. patients but also companions – where applicable) be informed in advance of any processing operations that are to be carried out on their data. The nature and the contents of the information that must be provided to the data subjects are set forth by the GDPR in Articles 13 and 14 and are usually conveyed to the data subjects via information notice. Depending on whether the information has been collected directly from the data subjects themselves, or from third parties (e.g. patient’s companion), the notice will contain slightly different information and will be provided at different times. And so, where personal data are collected directly from the data subject, the notice should be provided to at the time the personal data are obtained from the data subject. If the data is collected from third parties – the information notice should be provided to the data subject no later than within one month of the data collection.

The information that must be provided to data subjects under Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR includes:

- identity and contact detail of the data controller/joint controllers (and – if applicable - their representatives; DPOs – if appointed);
- the source from which the data originated (if collected not from the data subject himself) and if applicable, whether it came from publicly accessible sources;
- the purpose of processing;
- the legal basis for processing (such as e.g. consent);
- the categories of recipients of data (if any; e.g. external vendors/processors);
- in cases where the controller/joint controllers intend to transfer personal data outside the EEA, justification for such transfer along with the reference to appropriate safeguards and the means to obtain access to or a copy of those;
- data storage duration, or criteria used to determine such storage duration;
- data subjects’ rights and how to exercise them;

- the right to withdraw consent (where consent was the basis for processing) and that such withdrawal will not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent that took place before its withdrawal;
- the right to lodge a complaint with a competent supervisory authority;
- the existence of profiling including meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject;
- the possibility that the data will be further processed for scientific research purposes.

As already explained above, the above information must – in compliance with the transparency principle – be concise, transparent, intelligible and easily accessible in order to avoid information fatigue for the data subjects, who must consider many elements, sometimes fairly technical.

The REBECCA consortium should therefore strive to provide the above information in as clear and plain language as possible, in the language understandable to the research participant.

The information should also be provided free of charge, ahead of the processing, either in writing, or orally.

In the context of REBECCA, the information notice should preferably be attached to the double consent form¹⁴ presented to the research participants. It should also be made easily available and accessible (both on the REBECCA's website and in the mobile apps; a copy of this information could also be provided to the research participants in paper or electronic form/pdf attachment to an e-mail). Similarly, should REBECCA ingest and process personal data of the patient's companion (e.g. name, surname, contact details, relation to the patient), then the companion should also be provided with an appropriate information notice (e.g. via the companion app dashboard).

As far as the data collected via wearables, mobile app or web browser plugin, are concerned, the information notice could and should be provided in the user dashboard or attached to the terms of use of the wearable/the app/plugin or made available on the website to which the wearable will direct the patient.

¹⁴ Including the consent for processing under the GDPR as well as the consent to participate in the research study.

3.1.9 Data subject's rights

In order to assure data subjects, that the privacy of their personal data is properly safeguarded, GDPR empowers data subjects with certain rights. Through these rights, data subjects can make a specific request and obtain assurance that their personal data is not being misused for anything other than the legitimate purpose for which they originally provided it to the controller. The fundamental rights granted to data subjects under the GDPR are as follows:

- Right to **withdraw consent** (Article 7.3 of the GDPR)

Where processing is based on data subject's consent, the data subject has the right to withdraw his/her consent at any time. He/she shall be informed of this possibility prior to granting consent. GDPR requires that the withdrawal of consent be as easy as it was to grant it and urges, that the withdrawal shall not affect the lawfulness of the processing which took place prior to the withdrawal.

In the context of REBECCA this right should be assured by giving the research participants the option to withdraw from the clinical study they participate in at any point in time for whatever reason. They should be informed of this right at the time of collection of their consent (i.e. in the information notice attached to the consent form or in the user dashboard with regards to data processed in the mobile app and web browser plugin). It should be as easy to withdraw consent, as it was to grant it in the first place. Given the chosen means of obtaining consent for the REBECCA project (interview and signing of the consent form), research participants should be able to withdraw their consent in the same manner, that is by providing a written statement, expressing their wish to withdraw. Data subjects must be appropriately informed as to the consequences of the withdrawal of their consent. In practice, this means that the research participant who withdraws his/her consent, is made aware that he/she could no longer participate in the study nor use the REBECCA wearables or the mobile app, and that no new data concerning him/her will be collected. Also it should be made clear to the data subject who withdrew his/her consent, that the withdrawal shall not affect the lawfulness of the processing of his/her data that took place prior to the withdrawal.

- Right of **access** (Article 15 of the GDPR)

Data subjects have the right to obtain confirmation as to whether or not their personal data are being processed by the controller, and where that is the case, access their personal data. The controller shall provide a copy of the personal data undergoing processing. If the request is made by electronic means (and

unless otherwise requested by the data subject) the information should be provided to the data subject in a commonly used electronic form.

In the context of REBECCA, this means that the research participants shall have the right to inquire whether and what kinds of their data are being processed by REBECCA. The REBECCA partners, as joint controllers, should establish internal procedures on how to handle these types of requests.

- Right to **rectification** (Article 16 of the GDPR)

The data subjects have the right to obtain rectification of inaccurate (incorrect or misleading) personal data concerning them. They shall have the right to have incomplete data completed, including by means of providing supplementary statement. This right is closely linked to the controller's obligations under the accuracy principle (discussed above).

In the context of REBECCA this means that the REBECCA partners who are joint controllers should be prepared to handle such request of the research participants, that their data be up-to-date date, accurate and complete. Proper procedures allowing to verify the accuracy of the data processed within REBECCA and to handle these types of requests should be put in place by the REBECCA joint controllers. As with all data subject requests, the request to have the data rectified should be handled without undue delay however no later than within one month. The time to respond can be extended by two months if the request is complex or a number of requests have been received from the same research participant.

- Right to **erasure/"the right to be forgotten"** (Article 17, 19 of the GDPR)

Data subjects shall have the right to obtain from the data controllers the erasure of personal data concerning them without undue delay. The right is not absolute and only applies in certain circumstances, in particular where: (a) the data is no longer necessary for the purpose of processing for which it was collected, (b) when the data subjects withdrew their consent and there is no other valid basis for processing available to the controller, or (c) when the personal data have been unlawfully processed. Certain exceptions to the above exist, such as the necessity of the processing for scientific purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) of the GDPR (in so far as the exercise of the right to be forgotten is likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the objectives of that processing) or the necessity of the processing for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims.

In the context of REBECCA this means, that the research participants will be entitled to demand that their data be deleted from REBECCA system whenever any of the above mentioned circumstances materializes. In particular, they will be able to request to be forgotten whenever they withdraw their consent to participate in the research, and there is no other valid legal ground for continuous processing. If a valid erasure request is received by the REBECCA partners, and no exemption applies, then the REBECCA partners will have to erase the data (including from both live and backup systems (if any)). Research participants will have to be informed as to what will happen to their data when the erasure request is fulfilled in respect to REBECCA (and if applicable - that the data will remain within the backup environment for a certain period of time until it is overwritten). REBECCA partners (joint controllers) will have to communicate the erasure to each recipient to whom the data have been disclosed.

- Right to **restriction of processing** (Article 18, 19 of the GDPR)

Data subjects shall have the right to obtain the restriction of processing whenever:

- they contest the accuracy of their data (for the period enabling the controllers to verify the accuracy);
- the processing is unlawful but the data subjects oppose the erasure of their data and requests the restriction of their use instead;
- the controller no longer needs personal data for the purposes of the processing but the processing is required by the data subjects for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims.

In the context of REBECCA this means, that whenever any of the above materialize, REBECCA partners should implement measures that will restrict the processing of the data. This can be done by temporarily moving the data to another processing system or by making it unavailable to the users (i.e. patient's doctor on the dashboard). It should be noted within the system, that processing of the data has been restricted. No changes or modifications can be made to the data that has been restricted for processing. All recipients, who have received the data, must be informed of the restriction of processing. The data subject should be notified before the restriction is lifted. As with other data subject's requests, controllers should handle the request for restriction of processing without undue delay, no later than within one month. In certain exceptional cases, the time to handle the request can be extended by further 2 months.

- Right to **data portability** (Article 20 of the GDPR)

Data subjects shall have the right to receive their personal data, which they provided to the controller, in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and transmit that data to another controller without any hindrance. However, this right shall be available only where the processing is carried out based on consent, or if necessary for the performance of a contract and if carried out by automated means, and is limited by the rights and freedoms of others (i.e. it shall not adversely affect the rights and freedoms of others), including trade secrets or intellectual property (in particular the copyright protecting the software). However, the result of those considerations should not be a refusal to provide all information to the data subject. In the context of REBECCA, the exercise of this right could theoretically take the form of the research participant requesting certain data collected from him to be transferred to another controller, for example a medical professional not involved in REBECCA. In this case the research participant could request that the REBECCA partners provide him/her with the copy of his/her personal data that he/she provided directly to the REBECCA consortium¹⁵ in an accessible and machine-readable format (for example as a csv file) or that his/her data be transmitted directly (if technically feasible). Before doing this however, REBECCA partners should confirm the identity of the data subject. Once again – the request should be handled without undue delay no later than within one month. This could be extended up to an extra 2 months in exceptional circumstances (however, if this were to be the case, the data subject should be notified of the extension prior to the lapse of the first month along with the explanation for the extension).

- Right **to object** (Article 21 of the GDPR)

Data subjects shall have the right to object, at any time, on grounds relating to their particular situation, to the processing of their personal data carried out on the following grounds only:

- where the processing is necessary for the performance of task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller (Article 6.1 (e) of the GDPR) or

¹⁵ This does not encompass any data that was created by the controller himself: i.e. data derived, interpreted and assessed from the data provided directly by the patient. For example the right to portability would not apply to data which resulted from profiling. In the context of REBECCA it would not apply to various emotional, behavioural, living environment indicators created by REBECCA algorithms).

- where the processing is necessary for the purpose of the legitimate interest pursued by the controller or by a third party, so long as those interests are not overridden by the interests and fundamental rights of the data subjects (Article 6.1 (f) of the GDPR).

This includes profiling based on the above provisions.

The controller shall cease the processing of the personal data unless the controller can demonstrate compelling legitimate grounds for the processing which override the interests, rights and freedoms of the data subject or for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims.

In the context of REBECCA, this right seems of little relevance, as the processing of personal data will be carried out on a different basis (i.e. consent).

3.1.10 Profiling

The principles of fair and transparent processing require that the data subjects (i.e. REBECCA research participants) be informed of the existence of the processing operations and their purpose. In particular, they should be informed of the existence of profiling.

Profiling means any form of automated processing of personal data consisting of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict aspects concerning that natural person's performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behaviour, location or movements.

Since REBECCA research involves social-media based user profiling, which aims at extracting emotional indicators of the research participants based on their online activities, research participants should be informed of the existence of such profiling through the information notice incorporated on the consent form as well as in the REBECCA website privacy policy, the REBECCA web browser plugin and the REBECCA mobile apps (both pApp and cApp).

Social-media based user profiling in REBECCA

As a result of cancer, patients may suffer from anxiety, stress, depression, and other mental health issues. Online interactions can convey cognitive and emotional state. Patients are accustomed to expressing their thoughts and feelings through social media and they usually search for their symptoms on the web (forums, search engines, etc.).

Analysing the online activity of patients (both their browsing history as well as their activity in social media) provides information about their cognitive and emotional state

and allows to predict the deterioration of their emotional well-being. Doctors can exploit the predicted emotional state of patients to take action, such as arranging visits at the hospital or providing consulting to them. Doctors can also see how the treatment can affect the emotional well-being and try to find new ways to overcome the adverse effects. To this end, REBECCA's goal is to create an emotional indicator (for each individual patient) which will represent that patients' emotional state based on the patient's online activity.

For the above purpose, REBECCA will implement a web plugin, that will be installed on the patient's PC/laptop.

In order to enable the online activity monitoring the patient will have to express his/her explicit consent (by clicking on the consent tick box) to the monitoring of his online activity. The patient will be able to pause and resume monitoring (e.g. in order to stop monitoring whether he/she conducts research on the symptoms of another person). The patient will also have access to the collected data (URLs and queries, visits, comments, reactions, etc.).

By consenting to install the REBECCA plugin, the patient will allow REBECCA to collect prospective data on his/her online activity on:

- Facebook (queries, comments, reactions, visits)
- YouTube (queries, comments, reactions)
- Web browsing history (queries, websites visited).

No directly identifiable personal information (e.g., names, IPs) will be stored within the REBECCA 360° platform. The data ingested will be pseudonymized: a unique ID will be assigned to the patient, with the key allowing to re-identify the patient being held outside the REBECCA system, by the patient's doctors).

A dashboard will allow each patient to view all the data collected by the plugin from his/her online activities. Patients will be able to delete and thus exclude from analysis specific records of data they feel uncomfortable with (for example if they run a research on somebody else's symptoms or when someone else uses their device). Data will be then directly transmitted to the REBECCA server via secure and encrypted SSL, for the purpose of extracting the patient's emotional indicator (through algorithms that extract feelings from texts).

Access to stored patients' data is restricted. Under no circumstances will the clinicians (i.e. doctors and nurses) be allowed to view raw data of the patient's online activity. Instead, they will be able to see only the predicted emotional indicator of the patient. And since they hold the key to identify the patient, they will be able to match the indicator to their patient.

Although no directly identifiable personal information is requested or stored by the plugin at any point, it cannot be excluded that patients' online actions will reveal their identity (such as for example via their location data). This cannot be excluded and the plugin will record such interactions (e.g., a web search for "gyms near Gerd-Ragna Bloch Thorsens"). In such cases, this data could be processed within the patient's edge device only and not be transmitted to the REBECCA server.

A more detailed description of the web based user profiling can be found in section 3.4 of the D2.1 deliverable titled "Initial system specifications".

User profiling based on smartphone and wearable device data

Cancer, as well as primary treatment for cancer, can significantly affect the behaviour of a BCP in multiple ways. In particular, they can affect physical condition, mobility, outgoing behaviour, appetite, sleep quality, and various other aspects. Because of this, the REBECCA 360° monitoring platform will monitor and collect various "signals" of primary information, from which detailed analysis for the behaviour of each individual BCP can be extracted. To this end, a smartphone application will be used to collect such signals and information from the BCP's smartphone, and a wearable device will be used to collect physiological signals.

In particular, the wearable device collects signals relevant to motion, as well as to heart-rate. From these base signals, a variety of physical indicators can be extracted, such as number of steps, detection of exercise sessions (including type of exercise and intensity), recognition of type of physical activity (including level & intensity), recognition of transportation mode during trips, estimation of heart-rate variability and resting heart-rate, detection of stress moments, and more.

The smartphone application will collect continuously the geographical co-ordinates of the BCP, as well as her answers to questionnaires and photographs (including annotations) that she manually contributes. Location information can be used to extract a lot of indicators such as time spent at home, time spend at work, missing work (or working from home), preference of transportation mode, visits to specific types of places (such as restaurants or parks/recreational facilities) and potential increase or reduction in frequency of visits to such places.

It is important to note that these indicators will be presented only to the BCP and her clinician, and only after some level of processing. In particular, while the exact geographical co-ordinates will be stored internally in the REBECCA server, these will never be shown to anyone. Instead, only an abstract level of information will be presented. For example:

- time spent at home/work: in order to compute this indicator, the REBECCA system needs to know the address of the BCP's home or work. However, the addresses will never be shown to anyone, and will never be available for export. Instead, only the time that is measured (by the system) that BCP is at those locations will be available to the clinician;
- visits to restaurant: again, for the REBECCA system to compute this indicator, it needs to know the exact geographical location of the BCP over time. However, once the system detects a visit to a place and identifies that this place is a type of restaurant, it will only show this information. The exact location, name, and other identifiable information about the restaurant will never be shown. As a result, it is not possible (for the clinician) to infer the exact location of the BCP based on this indicator.

Various views of the data and their time evolution will be available both to the patient, via the smartphone application, and to the clinician, via the web-based interface.

Please see Section 3.2.4 titled "Use of location data by REBECCA" which discusses the requirements for the use of location data in the context of Rebecca.

3.1.11 Records of data processing operations

As part of the accountability obligation, data controllers are obliged to maintain a written (incl. electronic form) record of processing activities under their responsibility. Such records should be made available to the supervisory authority on request.

Article 30 of the GDPR lists exceptions to the above requirement, such as when the controller employs fewer than 250 persons. However, whenever the processing is not occasional, includes special categories of data (such as e.g. health related data) or is likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects, maintaining such record is compulsory, regardless of the number of employees.

Customarily records of processing operations contain the following information:

- Joint controllers' names and contact details (as well as those of the DPO);
- Purposes of processing;
- Description of categories of personal data and data subjects;
- Categories of recipients;
- If relevant: transfers to third countries;
- If possible, storage duration;
- If possible, security measures implemented;
- Data subjects' complaints/requests and how they have been handled;

- Information on data breach incidents, their consequences and mitigation measures.

All of the concerned partners of the REBECCA consortium already maintain (and if not – should maintain) such records, which include the processing operations conducted in connection with REBECCA.

3.1.12 Data breach handling and notification procedures

It is the duty of the joint controllers, to implement procedures to handle and notify data breaches to the appropriate data protection supervisory authorities as well as to provide communication on such breaches to the data subjects affected, whenever such breaches are likely to result in high risk to the rights and freedoms of those data subjects. Additionally, the joint controllers' are obliged to document any personal data breach, comprising the facts relating to that data breach, its effects and the remedial actions taken thereafter (see section "Records of data processing operations" above).

The procedure to be followed by the REBECCA partners, in case of a security breach affecting the personal data shared by them within the framework of REBECCA, will be set forth in the joint controllership agreement to be entered into between the partners.

3.1.13 DPIA

A Data Protection Impact Assessment is a formal process designed to systematically analyse, identify and minimize the data protection risks of a given project. It is a key part of the data controller's accountability obligations under the GDPR. If done properly, a DPIA allows controllers to assess and demonstrate their compliance with the data protection laws.

According to Article 35 of the GDPR, a DPIA must be carried out prior to processing, whenever a given data processing activity (especially one that involves new technologies) is expected to result in high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, considering the nature, scope, context, and purposes of that processing. In particular a DPIA must be carried out in case of:

- a systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons which is based on automated processing (including profiling), and on which decisions that produce legal effects concerning the natural person are based (or which similarly significantly affect the natural person);
- processing on a large scale of special categories of data referred to in Article 9(1), or of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 10; or
- a systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale.

Not only does the REBECCA action involve processing on a large scale of sensitive, health related data, but the research itself involves social media based user profiling.

Therefore, a DPIA must and will be conducted by the REBECCA consortium, as required under Article 35 of the GDPR.

3.1.14 Data transfers outside the EEA

Norway is a member of the European Economic Area. Since the GDPR has been incorporated into the EEA agreement via a decision of the EU-EEA joint committee, Norway shall not be deemed third country within the meaning of Article 45 of the GDPR. Therefore any transfers of personal data within REBECCA to Norway could take place without any restriction.

Irrespective of the above however, no personal data will be transferred to Norway within the framework of REBECCA.

As far as transfers from Norway (SUH) to other REBECCA partners located within the EEA are concerned (e.g. transfers to technical partners), these will take place based on the existing Norwegian "Personal Data Act" (Lov 15. juni 2018 om behandling av personopplysninger), which incorporates the GDPR to local law and governs the transfer of personal data to third countries, including those within the European Economic Area.

Irrespective of the above, the consent form will include the consent for transferring of data from Norway to the consortium institutions located in other EEA countries.

3.1.15 Appointment of a Data Protection Officer

All consortium partners that will store or access personal data have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO). The contact details of the respective DPOs will be shared with the subjects during the studies and will be available on the REBECCA website as well as in the REBECCA mobile applications.

3.1.16 Appointment of Ethics and Data Protection Team

In order to ensure that appropriate data protection procedures are in place when breast and prostate cancer survivors are recruited for the REBECCA evaluation studies, and that the EC is provided with all of the appropriate ethical approvals, including the collection and management of retrospective and prospective data, the Ethics and Data Protection Team (EDPT) was appointed within the REBECCA consortium. The EDPT includes Associate Prof. Ioannis Ioakimidis (KI), Dr. Kristin Jonsdottir (SUH), Senior Lecturer Theodoros Foukakis (RSTO), Prof. Jos Dumortier (Timelex), Dr Paraskevas Bourgos (INTRA), Dr. Symeon Papadopoulos (CERTH) and Dr. Christos Diou (HUA).

3.2 ePrivacy

3.2.1 Principles of the ePrivacy Directive

The ePrivacy Directive¹⁶ concerns the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector and deals with the regulation of a number of important issues such as confidentiality of information, treatment of traffic data, spam and cookies.

The key principles of the ePrivacy Directive are as follows:

- Where the e-Privacy Directive provides for a specific rule applicable to natural and legal persons in relation to processing in connection with the provision of publicly available electronic communications services in public communication networks, it prevails over the general rule set out by the GDPR (Principle of Specialty).
- Electronic Communication Services and Networks must be secured through appropriate technical and organizational measures. (Principle of Security).
- The confidentiality of communications and the related traffic data by means of a public communications network and publicly available electronic communications services, must be ensured (Principle of Confidentiality).
- Access to, or storage of, information on users' devices must be authorised by the users with a specific consent, unless it is "strictly necessary in order to provide a service explicitly requested by the subscriber or user" (the so called "cookie law", Prior Consent). In other words, any website, or app should provide clear information on the cookies it deploys into the users' devices and it should collect prior consent, where necessary.
- Principles applicable to Traffic Data
 - Traffic data must be erased or made anonymous when it is no longer needed for the purpose of the transmission of a communication or for the purposes of processing subscriber's billing and interconnection payments (**Traffic data erasure**);
 - Traffic data can be processed for marketing and/or for the provision of value-added services only upon specific consent of the user concerned (**Consent for Marketing purposes**);

¹⁶ Directive 2009/136/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2002/22/EC on universal service and users' rights relating to electronic communications networks and services, Directive 2002/58/EC concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector and Regulation (EC) No 2006/2004 on cooperation between national authorities responsible for the enforcement of consumer protection law available at https://edps.europa.eu/sites/default/files/publication/dir_2009_136_en.pdf

- Specific information on traffic data processing and its duration must be provided (**Specific Information**);
- Traffic data must be processed only by persons under the authority of the service provider that are dedicated to the function or unit for which such data are necessary (e.g. handling billing or traffic management, customer enquiries, fraud detection, marketing electronic communications services or providing a value-added service – **Authorisation profiles**).
- Principles applicable to Location Data
- Location data can be processed for the provision of value-added services¹⁷ only anonymously or upon specific consent of the user concerned (**Consent for Location Data**¹⁸);
- Users must be given the opportunity to easily refuse such processing at each connection (**Updated Consent**);
- Location data must be processed only by persons under the authority of the service provider that are dedicated to the function or unit for which such data are necessary (Authorisation profiles).

The ePrivacy Directive is a legal act of the European Union that requires member states to achieve a particular result without dictating the means of achieving that result. It has therefore been implemented into national laws and regulations.

Currently a new proposal – an ePrivacy Regulation is underway. If adopted, the ePrivacy Regulation will repeal the ePrivacy Directive, and will become immediately effective as law in all member states (superseding all of the national laws, that have implemented the ePrivacy Directive).

3.2.2 Applicability of ePrivacy principles to REBECCA

The general obligations derived from the ePrivacy Directive apply to the processing of personal data with regards to the provision of publicly available electronic communications services in public communications networks in the EU.

¹⁷ 'value added service' means any service which requires the processing of traffic data or location data other than traffic data beyond what is necessary for the transmission of a communication or the billing thereof.

¹⁸ Article 9.1 of the DIRECTIVE 2002/58/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communication) available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32002L0058&from=EN>

An electronic communications service is defined as “a service normally provided for remuneration, and which consists wholly or mainly in the conveyance of signals on electronic communications networks, including telecommunications services and transmission services in networks used for broadcasting, but exclude services providing, or exercising editorial control over, content transmitted using electronic communications networks and services; it does not include information society services, as defined in Article 1 of Directive 98/34/EC, which do not consist wholly or mainly in the conveyance of signals on electronic communications networks.”

The data analytics tools in REBECCA do not fall within the scope of the above definition, since they do not involve “wholly or mainly the conveyance of signals”. The primary function of the REBECCA platform (data analytics tools) is to perform analytics on data, rather than the conveyance of signals. Consequently, most obligations that apply to providers of electronic communications services will not be applicable to the REBECCA project.

The ePrivacy Directive could be used to protect the privacy of REBECCA’s web-based communication channels. It could also serve as the basis for drafting the Privacy and Cookie Policy of the REBECCA website and the mobile apps.

The privacy policy will be accessible via the REBECCA website or mobile app/plugin user dashboard and in accordance with the GDPR, it will provide detailed information relating to, in particular, the sharing of data within the REBECCA consortium (i.e. the essence of the joint controllership agreement) and will explain to users, the REBECCA’s policy and practices regarding the collection, use and disclosure of users’ personal information (see section 3.1.8 “Information notice”).

3.2.3 Cookies and other online tracking technologies

The ePrivacy Directive is also known as the “EU cookie law” as it concerns the use of cookies and other tracking technologies that websites and apps use. According to it, all websites in the EU must collect their visitors’ consent in order to place cookies on the users’ computers or smartphones (devices). That means, that if a website uses cookies for purposes like statistics and/or marketing, the site must ask the user for his or her consent before placing the cookies, the consent being based on “clear and comprehensive information” (so called “opt-in”/active consent). Also, the upcoming ePrivacy Regulation sets forth further rules on the use of cookies and clarifies that the user consent for cookies must be based on a meaningful choice (this is not the case when it comes to cookie walls – where users must consent to non-essential cookies in order to be allowed to access the site).

The REBECCA cookie policy should be accessible via the REBECCA website (i.e. in the website privacy policy) and in the REBECCA app/plugin user dashboard. In compliance with the data protection and the ePrivacy legislation, it should clearly explain to its users:

- what the cookies do;
- what the potential consequences of allowing the cookies are (i.e. that the users will be able to disable non-essential cookies); and
- why REBECCA is using them.

REBECCA should also obtain informed consent from users prior to deploying cookies (except for technically necessary cookies). The cookie consent will have to be active and meaningful (opt-in as opposed to pre-checked boxes).

3.2.4 Use of location data by REBECCA

One of the objectives of REBECCA is to improve the quality of life of the patients by in-depth analysis of their behaviour. In particular, REBECCA will attempt to do that by quantifying the life-space of the patient by monitoring patient's local environment and identifying places of importance to him/her (such as parks, cafes, restaurants, recreational facilities, workplaces).

In order to be able to do that, REBECCA will need access to the location services on the patient's end device (mobile) to continuously monitor the local environment of the patient. For that purpose, REBECCA partners should bear in mind that:

- Patient's consent for the use and access to location data must be obtained in advance; the consent must be valid, i.e. must be freely given, specific and informed (as already described above in Section 3.1.6 "Legal basis for processing"), for example patient can express it by ticking a box (in any case it must be an explicit opt-in, affirmative action).
- Patient must be informed of the details of the processing, prior to giving consent (i.e. the REBECCA app should inform what location data will be collected and processed, the purpose for which it will be processed and whether the location data will be shared with any third parties).
- Patient must be able to withdraw the consent and stop the use of location data at any time (an option to disable the location data within the mobile app settings should be available when starting the app).
- Location data should only be used for a specific reason (here: quantifying the life-space of the patient), and only for the duration necessary for the purpose.

3.3 REBECCA solution and the Medical Devices Regulation

Although REBECCA is not intended to be a medical device, a high level overview of the Medical Device Regulation (which covers not only the existing medical devices but also clinical investigations concerning such medical devices) is presented below for partners' consideration, as this might be addressed by the ethical committees.

3.3.1 Definition of a "medical device"

The European legal framework on "medical devices" is currently embodied in the European Medical Devices Regulation (Regulation),¹⁹ which lays down rules concerning the placing, making available on the market or putting into service of medical devices for human use and accessories for such devices in the European Union.

The Regulation also applies also to clinical investigations concerning such medical devices conducted in the EU.

According to the Regulation 'medical device' shall mean any instrument, apparatus, appliance, software, implant, reagent, material or other article intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for human beings for one or more of specific medical purposes, the most prominent one being the diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment or alleviation of disease²⁰.

The determining factor to distinguish a medical device from any other kind of device is the intention of the manufacturer. The term 'intended purpose' means the use for which a device is intended according to the data supplied by the manufacturer on the label, in the instructions for use or in promotional or sales materials or statements and as specified by the manufacturer in the clinical evaluation.

Software in its own right, when specifically intended by the manufacturer to be used for one or more of the medical purposes set out in the definition of a medical device, qualifies as a medical device (as opposed to software for general purposes, even when

¹⁹ REGULATION (EU) 2017/745 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC available <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32017R0745&from=EN>

²⁰ For a complete list of those specific medical purposes see definition of „medical device“ under Article 2 (1) of the Medical Devices Regulation available at [REGULATION \(EU\) 2017/ 745 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL - of 5 April 2017 - on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/ 83/ EC, Regulation \(EC\) No 178/ 2002 and Regulation \(EC\) No 1223/ 2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/ 385/ EEC and 93/ 42/ EEC \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32017R0745&from=EN)

used in a healthcare setting, or software intended for lifestyle and well-being purposes – which are not medical devices).

REBECCA 360° patient monitoring platform is a data collection system which is intended specifically to monitor breast cancer patients and provide information which will be then used to take decisions with diagnostic or therapeutic purposes.

Although it is not the intention of the REBECCA partners, that the REBECCA solution be treated as a medical device, it cannot be excluded with certainty, that some of its components, would not qualify as a medical device within the meaning of MDR. In particular the REBECCA 360° platform, which will undoubtedly serve medical purposes (i.e. will allow doctors to monitor and provide custom tailored treatment of the breast cancer patients) may be viewed by the ethical committees as a medical device within the meaning of the MDR.

Therefore, in anticipation of the above, partners should ensure that REBECCA system meets the requirements of clinical investigations under the MDR.

3.3.2 Requirements of clinical investigations under the Medical Devices Regulation

It cannot be denied that the intended purpose of REBECCA system is to monitor breast cancer survivors and provide information which will be then used to take decisions with diagnostic or therapeutic purposes.

As a consequence, it is highly advisable that the clinical studies undertaken in the framework of REBECCA observe the requirements of clinical investigations under the Medical Device Regulation.

This Regulation uses the term “clinical investigation”, defined as “any systematic investigation involving one or more human subjects, undertaken to assess the safety or performance of a device”.

The Medical Devices Regulation distinguishes between two categories of clinical investigations:

- clinical investigations carried out as part of the clinical evaluation for conformity assessment purposes,

and

- other clinical investigations undertaken to assess the safety or performance of a medical device.

The first category of clinical investigations may be carried out only for medical devices which are completely ready to be put on the market, including packaging, usage

instructions, etc. Since this is not the case with REBECCA solution, the REBECCA studies²¹ envisaged, will necessarily fall under the second category, i.e. other clinical investigations undertaken to assess the safety or performance of a medical device. As such, the REBECCA study will need to fulfil the requirements of Art. 82 of the Regulation.

3.3.3 Article 82 of the Medical Devices Regulation

According to Article 82, clinical investigations which are NOT carried out as part of the clinical evaluation for conformity assessment purposes (such as the REBECCA study), shall only comply with a limited number of requirements. These are as follows:

- clinical investigations shall be designed and conducted in such a way that the rights, safety, dignity and well-being of the subjects participating in a clinical investigation are protected and prevail over all other interests and the clinical data generated are scientifically valid, reliable and robust.
- clinical investigations shall be subject to scientific and ethical review. The ethical review shall be performed by an ethics committee in accordance with national law. Member States shall ensure that the procedures for review by ethics committees are compatible with the procedures set out in this Regulation for the assessment of the application for authorisation of a clinical investigation. At least one lay person shall participate in the ethical review.
- a clinical investigation may be conducted only where all of the following conditions are met:
 - an ethics committee, set up in accordance with national law, has not issued a negative opinion in relation to the clinical investigation, which is valid for that entire Member State under its national law;
 - the sponsor, or its legal representative is established in the Union;
 - vulnerable populations and subjects are appropriately protected in accordance with Articles 64 to 68;
 - the subject or, where the subject is not able to give informed consent, his or her legally designated representative has given informed consent in accordance with Article 63;
 - the rights of the subject to physical and mental integrity, to privacy and to the protection of the data concerning him or her in accordance with Directive 95/46/EC are safeguarded;
 - the investigational device(s) in question conform(s) to the applicable general safety and performance requirements set out in Annex I of the MDR apart from

²¹ Studies of the REBECCA system i.e. studies 4,5 and 6 of the DoA

the aspects covered by the clinical investigation and that, with regard to those aspects, every precaution has been taken to protect the health and safety of the subjects. This includes, where appropriate, technical and biological safety testing and pre-clinical evaluation, as well as provisions in the field of occupational safety and accident prevention, taking into consideration the state of the art;

- the investigator shall be a person exercising a profession which is recognized in the Member State concerned as qualifying for the role of investigator on account of having the necessary scientific knowledge and experience in patient care. Other personnel involved in conducting a clinical investigation shall be suitably qualified, by education, training or experience in the relevant medical field and in clinical research methodology, to perform their tasks.

3.3.4 Informed consent

One of the most essential requirements in the above mentioned list of requirements for clinical trials of medical devices, is the requirement regarding the informed consent of the clinical trial participant.

The informed consent must comply with the rules laid down in Article 63 of the Regulation.

These are quite detailed and can be summarized as follows:

- informed consent shall be written, dated and signed by the person performing the interview and by the subject;
- informed consent shall be documented;
- adequate time shall be given for the subject to consider his or her decision to participate in the clinical investigation;
- information given to the subject shall:
- enable the subject or his or her legally designated representative to understand: (i) the nature, objectives, benefits, implications, risks and inconveniences of the clinical investigations; (ii) the subject's rights and guarantees regarding his or her protection, in particular his or her right to refuse to participate in and the right to withdraw from the clinical investigation at any time without any resulting detriment and without having to provide any justification; (iii) the conditions under which the clinical investigations is to be conducted, including the expected duration of the subject's participation in the clinical investigation; and (iv) the possible treatment alternatives, including the follow-up measures if the participation of the subject in the clinical investigation is discontinued;
- be kept comprehensive, concise, clear, relevant, and understandable to the subject or his or her legally designated representative;

- be provided in a prior interview with a member of the investigating team who is appropriately qualified under national law;
- include information about the applicable damage compensation system;
- include the Union-wide unique single identification number of the clinical investigation and information about the availability of the clinical investigation results;
- The information shall be prepared in writing and be available to the subject;
- In the interview special attention shall be paid to the information needs of specific patient populations and of individual subjects, as well as to the methods used to give the information;
- In the interview it shall be verified that the subject has understood the information;
- The subject shall be informed that a clinical investigation report and a summary presented in terms understandable to the intended user will be made available irrespective of the outcome of the clinical investigation, and shall be informed, to the extent possible, when they have become available. The requirement to obtain consent of the participants to a clinical study is, in almost all cases, also imposed by an ethical board or research committee, which functions at the level of a hospital, a hospital cluster. In some countries, ethical boards are organized at regional or, exceptionally, at the national level.

3.3.5 Implementation in the context of REBECCA

Written approval from the competent ethical board or research committee must be obtained for the REBECCA project in each institution where patients will be recruited for participation in the clinical study (i.e., Sweden, Norway and Spain).

The research participants will be contacted individually to enquire about their willingness to participate in the REBECCA study. Patients interested in participating in the study will be informed about study details and will provide written consents. The consent to the participation to the study and the consent to the processing of their personal data will be collected during this visit.

All recruited individuals have to complete and sign a consent form, written in their native language.

In cases of illiteracy, the patient will be informed about the content of the consent form by his/her escort or legal representative, who will complete and sign a verification form. It must be clear to all parties involved that a consent to participation to a trial or a clinical study cannot automatically be assimilated to a consent for the processing of personal data.

These two consents (consent for processing of personal data and the informed consent to participate in the study), while collected in one single document serve two different purposes and are required by different legislations. Consent for the processing of personal data is the legal base justifying the processing of personal data and special categories of such data as required under the GDPR, which has already been addressed above.

3.4 Cybersecurity concerns

3.4.1 NIS Directive

The NIS Directive is the first EU horizontal legislation addressing cybersecurity challenges. It is the cornerstone of the EU's response to the growing cyber threats and challenges which are accompanying the digitalization of our economic and societal life.

The Directive has three main objectives:

- Improving national cybersecurity capabilities
- Building cooperation at EU level
- Promoting a culture of risk management and incident reporting among key economic actors, notably operators providing essential services (OES) for the maintenance of economic and societal activities and Digital Service Providers (DSPs).

Operators of essential services

The Directive compels Member States to classify key entities in various critical infrastructure sectors as "Operators of Essential Services" (OES) and to ensure that these enterprises have reached a given level of security in terms of their IT systems, while imposing a binding reporting obligation on these entities to report incidents.

Secondly, and in addition to ensuring that a well-resourced CSIRT is in place, Member States will also be required to designate a National Competent Authority (or NCA) to manage reporting and compliance of the OES entities with the Directive.

The rationale is that impacts of security incidents in such services may cause major disruptions to economic activities and to society at large, potentially undermining user confidence and causing major damage to the economy of the Union.

The NIS Directive does not define explicitly which entities are to be considered as OES under its scope. Instead, it provides criteria that Member States need to apply in order to carry out an identification process to determine which enterprises will be considered operators of essential services and therefore subject to the obligations under the Directive.

According to Article 5(2), the criteria for the identification of the operators of essential services are the following:

- the entity provides a service which is essential for the maintenance of critical societal and/or economic activities;
- the provision of that service depends on network and information systems;
- an incident would have significant disruptive effects on the provision of that service.

Article 4(4) of the Directive states that an OES is a “public or private entity of a type referred to in Annex II” that meets above criteria. The sectors and sub-sectors subject to the provisions of the Directive include in particular the health care sector and health care settings such as health care providers (hospitals and private clinics). To this end, the clinical partners of the REBECCA consortium, which are such health care settings, might fall under the scope of the NIS Directive and national cybersecurity legislations.

The NIS Directive requires that Member States ensure designated operators of essential services:

- take appropriate and proportionate technical and organizational measures to manage the risks posed to the security of network and information systems in the provision of their service [Article 14(1)].
- take appropriate measures to prevent and minimize the impact of the incidents affecting the security of the network and information systems used in the provision of their service [Article 14(2)].

To help Member States develop a harmonized security policy for their OES, the NIS Cooperation Group has published reference security guidelines²². According to the agreed principles, the security measures must be: effective, tailored, compatible, proportionate, concrete, verifiable and inclusive.

Based on the Cooperation Group guidelines, each National Competent Authority has published a set of security requirements that OES must implement within their organization. It is the responsibility of the OES to be able to demonstrate to the National Competent Authority that they are applying the mandatory security principles and measures associated with those principles that allow for the protection of network and information security within their organization. In particular, OES is responsible for identifying the network and information systems that need to comply with the

²² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/nis-cooperation-group>

Directive's security requirements, which are to be agreed with the National Competent Authority.

The use of internationally accepted standards and specifications relevant to the security of network and information systems is encouraged in order to promote primary implementations of the requirements.

Incident Notification Requirements

According to Article 14(3), Member States must ensure that OES notify without any delay "any incident having a significant impact on the continuity of the essential services." Hence, the OESs should only notify serious incidents affecting the continuity of the essential service.

Article 4(7) defines an incident as "any event having an actual adverse effect on the security of network and information systems." The term 'security of network and information systems' is further defined under Article 4(2) as "the ability of network to resist, at a given level of confidence, any action that compromises the availability, authenticity, integrity or confidentiality of stored or transmitted or processed data or the related services offered by, or accessible via, those network and information systems."

Consequently, any event having an adverse effect not only on the availability but also on authenticity, integrity or confidentiality of data or related services could trigger the notification obligation. In fact, the continuity of the service can be compromised not only in cases where the physical availability is concerned but also by any other security incident affecting the proper provision of the service.

In order to determine the significance of the impact of an incident, Article 14(4) states that the following parameters shall be considered:

- the number of users affected by the disruption of the essential service
- the duration of the incident
- the geographical spread regarding the area affected by the incident.

3.4.2 National cybersecurity systems of Spain, Sweden, and Norway

Clinical Partners which are operators of essential services have to observe their relevant national cybersecurity related obligations related to the IT systems they use.

SPAIN

Details on the implementation of the NIS Directive in Spain can be found at <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/nis-directive-spain>. Details on the

Spanish cybersecurity framework can be found here: <https://cybilportal.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/SPAIN-CYBERINCIDENTS-NATIONAL-GUIDE.pdf>.

SWEDEN

Details on the implementation of the NIS Directive in Sweden can be found at <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/nis-directive-sweden>.

NORWAY

Although Norway is not obliged to implement the NIS Directive as the directive is not encompassed by the EEA Agreement, the Norwegian government considered the directive to be EEA relevant and acceptable in December 2016. A consultation paper on the implementation of a law proposal implementing the NIS directive was submitted for public review in December 2018.²³

Details on the cybersecurity framework of Norway and the obligations of providers of critical societal functions can be found at: [https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/national-cyber-security-strategies/ncss-map/Norway Cyber Security StrategyNO.pdf](https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/national-cyber-security-strategies/ncss-map/Norway%20Cyber%20Security%20StrategyNO.pdf).

3.5 Intellectual property rights to background and results of the REBECCA project

Management of knowledge and IPR issues as well as the terms and conditions of access to such IP in the case of exploitation beyond the scope and duration of the project have been set forth by the REBECCA partners primarily in the Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3.6 Impact of recently proposed EU Acts

3.6.1 Data Governance Act

The Data Governance Act (DGA) is a legislative proposal of the European Commission that aims to facilitate data-sharing across sectors and Member States. The proposal was announced as part of the 2020 European strategy for data and was officially presented on 25 November 2020.

²³

<https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/national-cyber-security-strategy-for-norway/id2627177/>

The purpose of the DGA is to create a framework that encourages greater re-use of data by increasing trust in data intermediaries²⁴ and strengthening various data-sharing mechanisms across the EU. It applies to “data” defined as “any digital representation of acts, facts or information”, not only personal data.

The DGA will enable the creation of and provide guidance on the EU-wide common, interoperable data spaces in such strategic sectors as energy, mobility or health.

The DGA covers both personal and non-personal data²⁵ and its main purpose is to safely enable the sharing of sensitive data held by public bodies.

In particular, the DGA sets out rules on:

- conditions for the re-use of public sector data that is subject to already existing safeguards (e.g. commercial confidentiality, IP, trade secrets, data protection) ; it sets out a number of obligations and restrictions that the public sector bodies²⁶ are subject to if and when they decide to allow to re-use certain data they hold for purposes other than the initial public task for which they were produced; for example, the DGA requires of the public sector bodies who decide to allow the re-use of their data, that they make the conditions for the re-use of publicly available; moreover, these conditions must be non-discriminatory, proportionate and objectively justified and may not restrict competition. Exclusive access arrangements are prohibited. Moreover, public sector bodies who do provide access must ensure that they preserve the protected nature of the data (e.g. by releasing data in anonymous form or using secure processing environments such as differential privacy or synthetic data);
- obligations of providers of data-sharing services (the so-called “data intermediaries”); in order to ensure independence of the data intermediaries, the DGA imposes a licensing regime whereby all intermediation service providers must notify the relevant competent EU member state authority of the intent to provide such services; moreover, intermediation services must be offered by a separate legal person (not offering other services), metadata about the service use cannot be used for other purposes than to develop the service

²⁴ Data intermediaries are organizations which set up commercial arrangements between data holders and data users without adding any extra value to the data themselves;

²⁵ “data” is defined in the act as “any digital representation of acts, facts or information and any compilation of such acts, facts or information, including in the form of sound, visual or audio-visual recording.” This is a broad definition that also includes personal data as defined in the GDPR.

²⁶ “Public Sector Bodies” are “the State, regional or local authorities, bodies governed by public law or associations formed by one or more such authorities or one or more such bodies governed by public law”.

or to prevent fraud/cyber risk), the intermediation service provider can offer tools to facilitate exchange of data – but must have approval of the data holder/ data subject to do this; the provider must ensure availability and interoperability with other intermediation services; etc.

- introduction of the concept of data altruism; the DGA sets out a voluntary registration scheme for data altruism organizations (i.e. entities which allow for the re-use of their data, without compensation, for the common good, such as for example for scientific research or improving public service); entities who do register as data altruism organizations (DAOs) will be able to promote themselves as recognized “DAOs”, which will give individuals and data holders the confidence to make data available to that organization; the DGA imposes certain obligations on recognized DAOs (e.g. they must be non- for profit bodies and must be established to meet objectives of general interest);
- restriction of transfers of non-personal data; data intermediaries and recognized DAOs will need to consider if third countries offer appropriate protections for non-personal data and will need to resist attempts by public authorities in third countries to access EU originating non-personal data. Additional restraints apply to the re-use of public sector data (e.g. if a re-user intends to transfer non-personal data to a third country, it has to notify the public sector body of this at the time that it requests re-use of the data; the re-use request may be granted only if the parties affected give permission to the transfer).

According to Article 31 of the draft DCA, fines are to be set and implemented by each Member State. Unlike the GDPR, the draft DCA does not prescribe the specific amounts and weighing factors applicable to the corresponding monetary sanctions, yet it provides that MS must ensure that the penalties are effective, proportionate and dissuasive.

The political agreement was reached on the Data Governance Act on 10th December 2021. The DGA will become applicable 15 months after the date of its entry into force.

In the context of REBECCA, the provisions relating to data altruism might be of relevance, if at any point in time, the partners (i.e. clinical sites/hospitals) decide to allow the re-use of their REBECCA generated datasets for further scientific research.

3.6.2 European Data Act

On February 23, 2022 the European Commission presented its proposal for a Data Act, a regulation which aims to maximize the value of data in the EU economy, “by ensuring

that a wide range of stakeholders gain control over their data and that more data is available for innovative use, while preserving incentives to invest in data generation”.²⁷

The proposal set forth the harmonized rules on:

- making data generated by the use of connected products or related services available to the user of these products or services;
- making data available by data holders to data recipients’
- making data available by data holders to public sector bodies or EU institutions, agencies or bodies in cases of exceptional needs (such as e.g. emergencies).

The proposed European Data Act regulates the sharing of personal and non-personal data and applies to a wide range of stakeholders such as:

- manufacturers of connected products or related services (i.e. services incorporated in or inter-connected with a connected product in such a way that their absence would prevent the product from performing one of its functions)
- data holders (defined as legal or natural persons having the right or obligation, in accordance with the Data Act, applicable EU law or national legislation implementing EU law to make available certain data); and
- cloud and edge service providers.

As a result, the Data Act lays down a number of obligations that apply to the above groups of stakeholders. In particular, it introduces:

- an obligation of the manufacturers of connected products and services to provide certain information about access to data generated through the use of those products and services
- an obligation to design those products and services in a way that data are by default easily, securely and (where relevant and appropriate” directly accessible to the user
- right for consumers to access and use data generated by their use of connected products or service and the right of access (upon user’s request) to such data
- in cases of mandatory (under the Data Act or other EU or national laws implemented thereafter) B2B data sharing, an obligation of a data holder to make data available under fair, reasonable and non-discriminatory terms and in a transparent manner
- an “unfairness test” – unfair contract terms, relating to data access that have unilaterally been imposed by an enterprise on a micro, small or medium sized enterprise would not be binding; a term is deemed unfair if it is of such a nature,

²⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/data-act-proposal-regulation-harmonised-rules-fair-access-and-use-data>

that its use grossly deviates from good commercial practice in data access and use, contrary to good faith and fair dealing.

- An obligation of the data holder to make data available, upon request, to a public sector body, or to an EU institution, agency or body, if they demonstrate an exceptional need to use the data requested (e.g. where it is necessary to respond to a public emergency).
- Obligation of the providers of data processing services to clearly include in their contracts clauses that support switching in between those services, to gradually withdraw switching charges and to respect interoperability requirements.

Although it may not be now apparent how this proposed data legislation could affect REBECCA, the consortium partners should consider the proposal and assess whether – if adopted – it would apply to the data generated by REBECCA.

3.6.3 Artificial Intelligence (AI) Act

On April 21, 2021 the European Commission published a draft law to regulate artificial intelligence (AI) in the European Union. The Artificial Intelligence Act imposes extensive documentation, training and monitoring requirements on AI tools and systems that fall within its scope. Any company with EU market exposure that develops or wishes to adopt machine-learning based software will fall under the purview of the AI Act.

The AI act shall apply extraterritorially to any provider or distributor of AI whose products or services reach the EU market. It creates new regulatory requirements for AI tools used in a variety of sectors, including in particular financial services, education, employment or medical devices.

The AI Act distinguishes three categories of AI uses: prohibited AI uses, high-risk AI uses, and systems with limited risk.

The first category of completely prohibited AI uses encompasses the following:

- AI systems that manipulate persons through subliminal techniques or exploit the fragility of vulnerable individuals (due to age, physical or mental disability), and could potentially harm the manipulated individual or third person;
- AI systems that serve for general purposes of social scoring, if carried out by public authorities; or
- AI systems that are used for running real time remote biometric identification systems in publicly accessible spaces for law enforcement purposes.

The second category of AI uses (i.e. the so-called high risk AI uses), encompasses those AI systems, which are used as a safety component of a product or are covered by one of 19 specified pieces of EU single market harmonization legislation (e.g., aviation, cars,

medical devices). Moreover, AI systems deployed in the following sectors are deemed by draft legislation to be high-risk: (a) critical infrastructure, where the AI system could put people's life and health at risk, (b) law enforcement, administration of justice, employment, worker management and self-employment; (c) educational and vocational settings where AI systems could determine access to education or professional training, (d) migration, asylum, border control, including verifying the authenticity of travel documents, (e) essential private and public services (incl. access to financial services such as credit scoring systems). This list can be further expanded by the EC.

The AI Act imposes a number of technical and regulatory obligations on organizations that develop or use high-risk AI systems. These include in particular the requirement to (a) implement safeguards against various types of biases in data sets, (b) to use prescribed data governance and management practices, (c) to ensure the ability to verify and trace back outputs throughout the life cycle of the system, (d) to incorporate provisions for acceptable levels of transparency and understandability for users of and appropriate human oversight over the given AI system.

Before any AI system in a high-risk sector can be placed on the EU market, it must undergo an ex-ante conformity assessment. For AI products and services governed by existing product safety legislation (e.g. cars, aviation, machinery, medical devices or toys), the AI Act's requirements will fall under the existing third-party conformity assessment structures and regulatory frameworks that already apply to that sector .

The AI Act imposes also mandatory post-market monitoring obligations for high-risk systems. Serious incidents or faults of the AI system which breach safety laws or fundamental rights must be reported to the national supervisory body. In case of a violation of the AI Act, regulators can mandate access to the source code of a high-risk AI system. High-risk systems that violate the Act can be forcibly withdrawn from the market by the regulator.

Most of the Act's regulatory obligations fall on the party that places the AI system on the market (the "provider"), which can be a third-party provider or a company developing the AI itself. Distributors, importers, users and other third parties are subject to provider obligations if they place a high-risk AI system on the market under their name or make a substantial modification to it, in which case the original provider is relieved of the responsibility.

Providers of AI systems that pose a 'limited risk' (such as chatbots), will be subject to transparency obligations (e.g. technical documentation on function, development, and performance) and may choose to adhere to voluntary codes of conduct. The

transparency obligations will in particular serve to allow users to make informed decisions about how they integrate an AI software into their products and/or services.

Lastly, AI systems that pose 'minimal or no risk', such as spam filters, will be permitted with no restrictions but providers will be encouraged to adhere to voluntary codes of conduct. The European Commission envisages that most AI systems will fall into this category.

Fines for non-compliance with the draft legislation can amount to up to EUR 30.000.000 or up to 6% of the total worldwide annual turnover for the preceding financial year (if the offender is a company).

The AI Act is expected to be finalised and enter into force in the second half of 2022, although a transitional period is expected to apply before the regulation takes effect.

4 Ethical framework

4.1 Ethics in research

Fundamental ethical principles apply to all scientific research and ethical issues may arise in all possible domains of scientific research. Ethics is a high priority in EU funded research and all activities implemented in the Horizon 2020 framework must comply with ethical principles, as well as with the relevant national, EU and international legislation.

Research ethics is of crucial importance in all scientific domains and basic ethics principles are constantly adapted to specificities of various research domains by different professional and/or academic associations such as for example the European Science Foundation²⁸.

Amongst the Golden Rules of Ethical Research Conduct relevant to the project research domain, are the following principles:

- Respect the integrity and dignity of persons.
- “Do no harm” principle which translates in particular into the requirement that all risks must be clearly communicated to the subjects involved.
- Recognize the individual’s rights to privacy, personal data protection and freedom of movement.
- Obtain informed consent and maintain continuous dialogue with research subjects.
- Respect the principle of proportionality: do not impose more than is necessary on your subjects or go beyond stated objectives.
- Build on the understanding that any benefits are for the good of society, and any widely shared expressions of concern about threats from the given research must be considered.

4.2 Ethics in Horizon 2020 projects

The Lisbon Treaty, which forms the constitutional basis of the EU, makes an explicit reference to the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (“The Charter”). The Charter focuses on the right to the integrity of a person²⁹, protection of personal

²⁸ ESF INTERNAL CODE OF CONDUCT available at https://www.esf.org/fileadmin/user_upload/esf/ESF-Code-of-conduct-22.12.21.pdf

²⁹ Article 3.1. Everyone has the right to respect for his or her physical and mental integrity;

data³⁰ and family life³¹ as well as rights in the field of bio-ethics³², academic freedom and freedom of scientific research³³.

Also the Regulation 1291/11-12- 2013, which establishes Horizon 2020, sets forth in its Article 19, the ethical principles applicable to all research and innovation activities under Horizon 2020. In particular, all Horizon 2020 projects should observe the principle of proportionality, the right to privacy and protection of personal data, the right to physical and mental integrity of a person, the right to non-discrimination and the need to ensure high levels of human health protection.

As far as the relation between the healthcare provider and the patient/research participants is concerned, this has been regulated by the World Medical Association (WMA) in their ethical guidelines contained in the "Declaration of Lisbon on the Rights of the patient" and the "Declaration of Helsinki", which specifically addressed the Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects.

4.3 Ethics in REBECCA

4.3.1 REBECCA participants' rights

In REBECCA, the decision regarding the research participation will be entirely voluntary, based on full disclosure and understanding of the participant (patient) and clinical trial information. There will be strict adherence to the requirements and procedures concerning provision of informed consent (for more on the requirements of informed consent please see Section 3.3.4), as approved by local ethical reviewing authorities (i.e. ethical committees in Sweden, Norway and Spain) and institutional guidelines (i.e. the Declaration of Helsinki). Prospective research participants will be adequately informed of the particularities of the studies (the aims, methods, sources of funding, possible conflicts of interest, institutional affiliations of the researcher, the anticipated benefits and potential risks of the studies, as well as the discomfort it may entail, post-study

³⁰ Article 8.1. Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her.

³¹ Article 7 Everyone has the right to respect for his or her private and family life, home and communications

³² Article 3.2. In the fields of medicine and biology, the following must be respected in particular: (a) the free and informed consent of the person concerned, according to the persons; (b) the prohibition of eugenic practices, in particular those aiming at the selection of persons; (c) the prohibition on making the human body and its parts as such a source of financial gain; (d) the prohibition of the reproductive cloning of human beings

³³ Article 13 The arts and scientific research shall be free of constraint. Academic freedom shall be respected.

provisions and any other relevant aspects of the study) as well as of their right to refuse to participate in the study or to withdraw their consent at any time without reprisal.

Clinical partners carrying out the REBECCA studies will collect prospective participants' consents in the form of a paper document, consisting of the information letter and a consent form, to be signed once all the details of the planned study protocols have been clearly communicated to the subject concerned.

4.3.2 Research Ethics Committees' approvals

Before any of the REBECCA studies begin, appropriate research protocols will be submitted for consideration, comment, guidance and approval to the national/regional research ethics committees.³⁴

REBECCA will gain access to the required retrospective data after the appropriate ethical permissions, which will describe the precise data structure and data handling, are obtained.

Also, a final report to the relevant ethics committees, containing the summary of findings and conclusions, will be also submitted upon the completion of the studies.

4.4 AI and causal modelling

4.4.1 Ethics requirements for Trustworthy AI

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to systems that show intelligent behaviour. By analysing their environment these systems can perform various tasks with some degree of autonomy to achieve specific goals. In essence, artificial intelligence systems act in the physical or digital dimension by perceiving their environment through data acquisition, interpreting the collected structured or unstructured data, reasoning on the knowledge, or processing the information derived from this data and deciding the best action(s) to take to achieve the specific goal that was given to the system.

Machine learning (i.e. a discipline that teaches machines using data), is one of the technical mechanisms that underpins and facilitates AI.

REBECCA will use causal modelling methodologies, combined with deep learning algorithms to study the interactions of comorbidities and lifestyle parameters in breast cancer patients. Specifically, REBECCA will develop graph-based models of the causal dependencies between clinical and lifestyle parameters in the breast cancer domain

³⁴ Sweden: The National Swedish Ethical Review Authority; Norway: The West Norwegian Regional Committee for Medical and Health Research Ethics; Spain: The Ethical Committee for Research with Medicines of the General University Hospital of Valencia

and will use deep learning and variational methods for modelling latent confounding factors from observational data (such as RWD). It will implement an innovative data management and analysis platform with capabilities for federated learning which supports training machine learning and causal models across distributed health data repositories. It will also develop signal processing and machine learning algorithms for comprehensive patient monitoring using RWD.

In February 2020, European Commission released “A White Paper on Artificial Intelligence – a European approach to excellence and trust”³⁵, the purpose of which was discuss policy options for how to achieve two goals: to promote the uptake of AI and to address the risks with certain uses of AI.

The paper proposes that trust and excellence are key elements of future data regulation policy in Europe. In regards to creating an ecosystem of trust, the white paper refers to the Ethics Guidelines, and in particular the seven key requirements for AI.

The European Commission identifies two categories of risks in AI:

- risks for fundamental rights (including data protection, due to the large amounts of data being processed, and non-discrimination, due to bias within the AI)
- risks for safety and the effective functioning of the liability regime.

The High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence provided the AI Ethics Guidelines to the Commission in March 2019. The AI Ethics Guidelines forms part of a vision embracing a human-centric approach to AI, which will enable Europe to become a globally leading innovator in ethical, secure and cutting-edge AI. It strives to facilitate and enable “Trustworthy AI made in Europe” that will enhance the wellbeing of European citizens.

The guidance is centred around the concept of “trustworthy AI”. Trustworthiness is defined “a prerequisite for people and societies to develop, deploy and use AI systems”. Without AI systems being trustworthy, unwanted consequences may arise and prevent the realization of the social and economic benefits of AI. The guidance puts forward 7 requirements for trustworthy AI:

- Human agency and oversight

AI systems should support human autonomy and decision-making, as prescribed by the principle of respect for human autonomy. AI systems should

³⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/commission-white-paper-artificial-intelligence-feb2020_en.pdf

support the user's agency, foster fundamental rights and allow for human oversight.

- Technical robustness and safety

AI systems should be developed with a preventive approach to risks and minimizing or preventing harm. They should be secure and resilient to attacks, should have safeguards that enable a fallback plan in case of problems and should produce accurate, reproducible and reliable results.

- Privacy and data governance

AI systems should guarantee privacy and data protection throughout a system's entire lifecycle. Adequate privacy protection also necessitates data governance that covers the quality and integrity of the data used as well as data access protocols.

- Transparency

AI systems should be transparent, in a way that data sets and processes are traceable and explainable. Moreover, people need to be informed when they are interacting with an AI system.

- Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

AI systems should ensure inclusion and diversity throughout the entire system's life cycle. It should avoid unfair biases which could lead to discrimination and should be designed in an accessible and universal way.

- Environmental and societal well-being

AI systems should be sustainable and ecologically responsible to the greatest extent possible. They should be used to benefit all human beings, including future generations

- Accountability

AI systems should be accountable. This necessitates that mechanisms be put in place to ensure responsibility and accountability for AI systems and their outcomes, both before and after their development, deployment and use.

These requirements should be continuously evaluated and addressed throughout the AI system's lifecycle.

When designing, developing and using artificial intelligence, REBECCA partners should assess the impact of this artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms on human rights, particularly the right to the protection of personal data, as well as human dignity and other fundamental values. This assessment should be part of a broader data protection impact assessment and should take into account the requirements set by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence. To this end, the 'Trustworthy AI Assessment List' incorporated in the guidance document of this group can be used.

4.4.2 Data-driven discrimination and data bias

When data and algorithms are used for decision making purposes, there is potential for discrimination against individuals. The Council of Europe "Study on discrimination, artificial intelligence and algorithmic decision-making"³⁶ points out that AI systems are often "black boxes": it is often unclear why a system makes a certain decision. Because of the opaqueness of such decisions, it is difficult for people to assess whether they were discriminated against on the basis of, for instance, their age or gender or racial origin. AI-driven decision-making can lead to discrimination in several ways.

For example, AI decision-making can have discriminatory results if the system uses biased training data. If data is poorly labelled, inaccurate, incomplete or if it reflects human prejudices, then the AI model will reproduce those same biases. Similarly, by selecting only certain features that an AI system uses for prediction, the organization might introduce bias against certain groups.

The European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights Study "#BigData: Discrimination in data-supported decision making"³⁷, offers the following solutions towards fundamental rights compliance in the development and use of data-driven AI, which should be followed by REBECCA:

³⁶ <https://rm.coe.int/discrimination-artificial-intelligence-and-algorithmic-decision-making/1680925d73>

³⁷ <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2018/bigdata-discrimination-data-supported-decision-making> p.11;

- being as transparent as possible about how algorithms are built and used;
- conducting fundamental rights impact assessments which include among others, an assessment of the potential for discrimination in relation to different grounds – such as gender, age, ethnic origin, religion and sexual or political orientation;
- checking the quality of data (algorithms used in machine learning systems and artificial intelligence (AI) can only be as good as the data on which they learn);
- making sure the way the algorithm was built and operates may be meaningfully explained.

5 Operational and patient restrictions and requirements

This section describes operational and patient restrictions and requirements. Operational restrictions and requirements are based on the limitations identified by technical partners regarding data collection, storing, processing, and management, computational resources, access to them for development purposes, and more. Patient restrictions and requirements include (a) requirements identified by the patients (as users of the system, i.e., user requirements) and (b) by the clinical partners (in combination with the technical partners); from these, the former (a) are covered in D1.1 “User requirements and use cases” and thus not repeated here, while the latter are related to patient management and are thus documented here.

5.1 Operational restrictions and requirements

Operational restrictions and requirements mainly regard constraints that are necessary to enable technical functionalities and features (such as the processing of the collected data). Unless these requirements are satisfied, such technical functionalities can become impossible to perform.

Below is a summary of the requirements and constraints of the REBECCA system as identified by the members of the consortium

5.1.1 Data access by technical partners

While the technical partners will not interact with the REBECCA system and data in the final version of the REBECCA system, it is required that members of the technical part of the consortium will have access to the collected data, both during the data-collection periods and after (but generally within the duration of the REBECCA project³⁸). This is an important requirement so that these members are be able to:

- monitor the data-collection process to ensure no technical issues arise (which can cause data loss);
- understand the nature and characteristics of collected data;
- explore them and design effective information-extraction algorithms;
- train large machine-learning models on local (i.e. in the premises of AUTH, CERTH, and HUA), but powerful, computing servers;

³⁸ In some exceptional cases (i.e. with respect to those of the REBECCA studies taking place near the end of the project) analysis of the data may be performed after the end of the REBECCA project itself.

- evaluate the developed algorithms and processes to assess the effectiveness and feasibility of the solutions.

As a result, researchers of the technical partners will require access to exported REBECCA datasets. These datasets will need to be transferred to Greece and processed by AUTH, HUA, and CERTH. Data minimization principle should be observed, meaning: only data necessary for the purposes of processing will be exported in these datasets. See section 3.1.5 above for more on data minimization principle.

5.1.2 Data storing and processing requirements

Both of the smartphone applications (the patient application/pApp and the companion application/cApp) will collect large amounts of data (such as ad hoc questionnaires, photos, and mainly continuous, high-rate time-series sensor signals from the wearable smart-watch) and transmit them to the REBECCA server.

While some behavioural indicators can be computed on the smartphones, there are indicators with high processing requirements (such as automatic eating detection based on the acceleration signal collected by the wearable smartwatch that requires Deep Neural Network inference on high-performance graphics processing units - GPUs). Such computations cannot be performed on wearable devices or the smartphone, as they have increased requirements in processing power, memory, and energy consumption.

Similarly, it is not possible for the web-browser plug-in to extract emotional indicators; browser-plugins only execute within the process of the web-browser and cannot support consistent computation times and access to resources. Furthermore, extraction of emotional indicators commonly requires Deep Neural Networks, and thus GPU processing power.

Finally, introducing heavy computation load on the user's devices would degrade the user experience of the system. As a result, the following requirements are introduced:

- the REBECCA server hardware and software (database) should efficiently store and retrieve large volumes of continuous (24h/day), high-rate (up to 50Hz), multidimensional time-series signals;
- the REBECCA servers should provide enough processing power and memory to enable the signal-processing and machine-learning algorithms to execute without issues, including high-performance GPUs.

The web-browser plug-in collects information regarding the user's online behaviour and browsing history. However, browser plug-ins do not typically have access to local storage (on the user's device), so, contrary to the case of the smartphone applications,

all data collected by the web-browser plug-in should be transmitted directly to the REBECCA servers, where it will be stored. However, even in the case of the smartphone applications, the collected signals from the wearable devices should be periodically removed (after they have been successfully uploaded to the REBECCA server) to avoid flooding the smartphones storage.

5.2 Patient restrictions and requirements

The user (i.e. BCPs) requirements for the REBECCA system have been identified in the context of T1.1 (which included co-creation workshops with the BCPs, large-scale collection of user requirements using online questionnaires, and the statistical analysis of the answers to the questionnaires). The questionnaires focused on various technological components of the REBECCA system, with the view to identify BCPs' preferences, familiarity, and expectations vis-à-vis the particular components of the envisioned REBECCA system.

All of those have been subsequently taken into account by the consortium partners during the design, structuring and development of the REBECCA system. In summary, the BCPs requirements as regards the REBECCA system related to:

- the BCPs' experience with the use of smartphones, smartwatches, wearables, and online systems, and their habits regarding online behaviours;
- the BCPs' approach to the use of the cApp (specifically, the reporting that will be provided by the patients' companions regarding their health status and well-being);
- the BCPs' attitude towards monitoring and sharing of their personal information;
- the preferred system functionalities (such as the type of behaviour that the monitoring tool of REBECCA would extract automatically).

These user requirements have been described in detail in Sections 4 and 5 of D1.1. "User requirements and use-cases". Thus, the remaining of this section focuses on patient-management restrictions and requirements, as identified by both clinical and technical partners based on discussions and feedback from the IT and legal departments of the hospitals that the clinical partners belong to.

5.3 Case Report Form (CRF) data

While the REBECCA system will be used within clinical trials, managing of patients will not be part of the system, as it is out of the scope of the project. Instead, traditional Case Report File (CRF) systems will be used, and data will be manually or automatically transferred from these systems to the REBECCA servers. To help reduce the complexity

of this task, however, a common CRF platform should be used by each site (of clinical trial).

Based on this planning, a set of restrictions arise regarding the management of BCPs within and out of the REBECCA system. Specifically:

- REBECCA system should not communicate programmatically (i.e. directly with software) with the existing CRF and EHR systems of the hospital and clinical partners;
- all historical medical data (i.e. EHR records) of the participating BCPs will be inserted in the REBECCA system by medical personnel (of the clinical partners) using specifically created interfaces (i.e. CRF templates), created by the technical partners;
- additional medical data, diagnoses, questionnaires, examination results, etc., that will be collected during trials, will also be inserted in the REBECCA system in a similar manner;
- personal identification, and any other kind of data that can link the entries in the REBECCA system to BCPs will not be inserted in the system; a mapping between the REBECCA system pseudo-IDs and the IDs of the patients will be maintained offline, at the clinical sites.

Based on discussions, clinical partners have agreed to use REDCap³⁹ as the “offline” (for the REBECCA system) CRF to collect all BCP data. This data will then be manually or automatically exported and inserted to the REBECCA system, in agreement with the requirements described above.

As REDCap server, we refer to the individual REDCap instances, that should be available at the premises of the clinical partners – SUH, INCLIVA, and RSTO. Installation and maintenance of the REDCap server is responsibility of these partners. REDCap will be used to collect clinical data and questionnaires during the clinical studies which will be collected at the clinical sites. For the purposes of data collection in REBECCA, and in coordination with HUA and 8BELLS, a common Case Report Form (CRF) template is being developed for the REBECCA studies. It is constructed as a “superset” that contains all variables across studies. Each clinical partner will adjust the common CRF template according to its protocols, i.e., by deleting not relevant fields or translating the field labels (but maintaining the common variable names of the fields). More details can be found in Section 3.5 of D2.1.

REDCap instances will communicate with the REBECCA server and transfer the collected data to the latter. REDCap offers the following ways to facilitate this communication:

³⁹ REDCap is a secure web application for building and managing online surveys and databases.

- each REDCap instance can be configured to expose a REST API through a URL, which is unique to each project (i.e., study). Instructions on how to securely configure this REDCap API are given in Section 3.1.3 of D2.1.
- each REDCap instance is configured to upload data to REBECCA whenever a change in the data occurs (e.g., new data are added). In this case, REBECCA system will expose a REST API⁴⁰ to consume the submitted data.
- Alternatively, data can be uploaded manually as files through the REBECCA UI⁴¹.

The first method is probably the most robust way of transferring REDCap data. The final decision will be taken by T2.2 in coordination with the clinical partners.

⁴⁰ API (i.e. application programming interface), is a set of rules that define how applications or devices can connect to and communicate with each other. A REST API is an API that conforms to the design principles of the representational state transfer (REST) architectural style.

⁴¹ UI means „User Interface“.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable has provided a detailed overview of the European and national frameworks for handling legal and ethical issues in Horizon 2020 research and innovation programmes such as REBECCA. It aimed to identify and address the key issues that can arise during the lifespan of the REBECCA project.

It first investigated corresponding EU laws, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), ePrivacy directive, the Medical Devices Regulation, the NIS Directive or the most recent proposals of the European Commission such as the Data Governance Act, the European Data Act or the AI Act. The deliverable identified the relevant challenges under the said legislation and suggested how to address those in the context of REBECCA. The ethical standards in research and Horizon 2020 programmes have also been discussed (including the use of Artificial Intelligence), allowing the consortium to introduce effective measures towards the prevention of ethical concerns that might occur in the context of REBECCA action. The deliverable finally described what operational restrictions should be accounted for when designing a system like REBECCA and how the technical partners plan to address those.

In doing the above, the deliverable serves as a guidance for the REBECCA partners, who will be designing and developing the REBECCA ecosystem.

This deliverable will be followed by continued interactions with partners and - where needed - more targeted legal aspects will be addressed by the REBECCA consortium.